

LEarning and action alliances for **NexuS** **E**nvironments
in an uncertain future

LENSES

WP2

D2.4. Report on LENSES strategic roadmaps for Nexus future

Manuel Bea, Estrella López & Tomás Vázquez (ECOADAPTA)

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 Organisation name of lead contractor for this deliverable: ECOADAPTA (PARTNER)
 Lead Author Manuel Bea Martínez (ECOADAPTA)
 Email manuelbm@ecoadapta.org
 Contributions from Estrella López Moya, Tomás Vázquez (ECOADAPTA)
 Menemen and Pinios pilots
 Internal Reviewers Raffaele Giordano, Alessandro Pagano (IRSA)
 Andreas Panagopoulos, Vassilios Pisinaras (SWRI)

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Foreword

The present deliverable relates to Task 2.3 of the LENSES project, "Visioning of prosperous Nexus communities", which aims to design and develop a series of visioning exercises for a subset of the LENSES pilot areas. These visions are defined as imaginative representations of a desirable future based on both aspirations and concerns, and will be represented through scenarios developed through a participatory planning process and backcasting techniques. The process will be synthesized into strategic roadmaps outlining strategies and actions to realize these long-term goals.

The initial version of the deliverable provided guidelines to facilitate the implementation of the visioning methodology by the pilot teams as part of the overall participatory process, with the primary objective of introducing the key concepts and essential resources and highlighting guiding questions and ways to co-produce nexus visions with stakeholders that can make the scenarios comprehensive, relevant, and useful to policy-makers, practitioners, and businesses.

A second version incorporating the main results of the visioning exercises in the form of key information to support the elaboration of strategic roadmaps has been produced by the end of the project. The deliverable is divided into six sections: the first outlines the theoretical framework for scenario co-production, the second proposes methodological steps for engaging stakeholders in the visioning approach, the third provides guidance on the planning and application of the visioning approach with the support of Work Packages 2 and 4, and the final sections (i.e., sections 4, 5 and 6) contain the results produced in the LENSES pilots that have applied the participatory scenario planning methods (i.e., Doñana, Menemen and Pinios).

Abbreviations

BAU: Business as Usual

CHG: Confederación Hidrográfica del Guadalquivir (Guadalquivir river basin authority)

CLD: Causal Loop Diagram

D: Deliverable

EBD: Estación Biológica de Doñana (Doñana's Biological research station)

JA: Junta de Andalucía (Andalusian regional government)

LAA: Learning and Action Alliances

PEA: Political Economy Analysis

PSDM: Participatory System Dynamics Model

RCP: Representative Concentration Pathways

WEF: Water-Ecosystems-Food

WP: Work Package

1. Background

1.1. Introduction

This deliverable is related to the Task 2.3 'Visioning of prosperous Nexus communities'. The task focuses on the design and development of a series of visioning exercises that will be undertaken by some of the LENSES pilots. These visions are defined as a picture or an imagination of a desirable future, (i.e. based upon hopes and dreams but also upon concerns and fears) rather than a forecast of the future. In the case of LENSES, the proposed approach is based on the identification of visions on a more resilient and integrated nexus approach to face the core challenges in each area.

The visions will be represented under the form of scenarios through a participatory planning process to be complemented with the use of backcasting techniques for building narratives that can lead from the business-as-usual scenario towards the consensual vision of the group of local and regional stakeholders. As a final step, this process will be synthesized in the form of LENSES strategic roadmaps describing bundles of strategies and actions that can support the achievement of the long-term desirable visions.

The initial version of the deliverable (M20) provided detailed guidelines to facilitate the implementation of the visioning methodology by the pilot teams as part of the overall participatory process within the frame of the LAAs. This initial version aimed at supporting LENSES pilot areas to promote the science/society/policy interface in the project, and to create capacity for the design of future scenarios and strategic roadmaps in decision-making. Thus, its core objective was not to develop all aspects related to scenarios in detail, but rather, to provide an entry point to core concepts and essential resources available. It aimed at highlighting guiding questions and possibilities to co-produce nexus visions with stakeholders that could make scenarios comprehensive, relevant, and useful to potential users (policy-makers, practitioners, businesses).

By the end of the project, a final version of this report has been produced, synthesizing the main results of the visioning exercises in LENSES pilot under the form of strategic roadmaps.

In a nutshell, the initial version of the deliverable produced guidelines and supporting material for the implementation of the LENSES visioning approach in some pilots whereas the final version incorporates the results from the application of the method in three LENSES pilots, i.e., key information and policy recommendations for the elaboration of several strategic roadmaps as a final output of the process.

The first part of the deliverable (i.e., section 1) outlines the foundations or theoretical framework that is needed to understand scenario co-production; **the second part** (section 2) proposes methodological steps to engage stakeholders in the visioning approach; **the third part** explains in which pilots the methods have been applied with the support of WP2 (LAAs) and WP4 (PSDMs); and the **last part (sections 4-6)** contain the results produced by the LENSES pilots.

1.2. Key concepts: visions, scenarios, and strategic roadmaps for Nexus future

As an initial step, this section defines and provide some generic information on key concepts used in the LENSES visioning approach, i.e., visions, scenarios, and strategic roadmaps.

1.2.1 Visions

A **desirable future or vision** refers to a scenario directed towards an image or narrative in which a set of agreed-upon objectives have been achieved, thus offering a positive image of the future. In other words, a 'vision' is an image of what is desirable for a community. The proposed method in LENSES for the construction of common visions is based on a participatory scenario exercise. Through this approach, we aim at co-developing with stakeholders several future visions for their pilots and elicit the sets of actions that are needed to materialise such visions. While there is flexibility in the number of visions to be co-developed in each pilot, the exploration of at least 2 contrasting visions and associated pathways, including a Business as Usual (BAU) and a Desired Future scenario (vision) is suggested (see [Figure 1](#)).

The main premise is that achieving a WEF security in a given pilot under climate change pressures is largely determined by decisions made by a wide range of state and non-state actors across many scales, ranging from local to national, regional, and even global decision makers. For this reason, the participatory scenario process distinguishes two main "spheres": "sphere of influence" and "sphere of uncertainty".

The "**sphere of influence**" refers to those sets of actions and policy solutions (i.e., pathways) that local, regional, and national actors can agree on and have the capacity to influence to materialise the proposed vision within a given pilot.

The "**sphere of uncertainty**" takes into consideration that countries, basins, and regions are also affected by the so-called global drivers, such as climate change, global prices, political instability, crisis, etc., which add significant challenges to any local and/or national planning process. This requires that local to national decision makers take them explicitly into account, ensuring that their proposed plans, solutions, and related pathways, are robust enough in the light of such global drivers.

Conceptual framework

Figure 1. Conceptual framework for the visioning exercise. The figure shows our aim to identify desired futures that may be achieved through specific pathways (i.e., set of well-defined actions and policies) under the uncertainty of global drivers –not specifically considered by these pathways. The visions provided a clear alternative to business-as-usual scenarios.

1.2.2 Scenarios

The analysis of **scenarios** can be defined as a study of events that may occur in the future, organized in a limited and structured list with the possible future situations. The use of scenarios has been recognised as a powerful tool for exploring plausible future dynamics and uncertainty in complex socio-ecological systems.

There are many **types of scenarios**¹, depending on the aim they are defined for and how they are built (see [Figure 2](#)):

- **Exploratory scenarios** answer questions such as: *if we assume certain conditions (consumption behavior, irrigation rates...) characterizing specific trajectories of drivers, what would be the effects on one or more specific variables?* Thus, this kind of scenarios examine a range of plausible futures, based on potential trajectories of direct and indirect drivers. Because of their flexibility, they are well suited to allow awareness-raising, problem identification, and agenda setting, and stimulate creative thinking.
- **Target-seeking or intervention scenarios** answer questions such as: *if a certain target is to be achieved (e.g. keeping a certain level of water, reducing biodiversity loss...), what are the possible pathways to reach this goal?* Therefore, their development may directly **contribute to policy design**. Based on an agreed-upon future target, they focus on how a desired future can be achieved, allowing to examine the viability and effectiveness of alternative pathways to a desired outcome. They start

¹ Goudeseune, L., Solerød, M., Aleksandrova, M., Asanica, A., Eggermont, H., Jacques, C., Le Roux, X., Lemaitre, F., Popa, A., Ungvári J. (2020). Handbook on the use of biodiversity scenarios. BiodivERSA-Belmont Forum report. 36 pp.

with the definition of a clear objective or a set of objectives that can be either specified in terms of targets or functions to be optimised.

- **Policy or management screening scenarios** answer questions such as: *What would have happened if other policy/ management options were considered?* These scenarios **are well suited for supporting the implementation of interventions**. They consider various policy or management options and are used to forecast the effects of alternative policy or management interventions. For example, in policy-screening scenarios, a policy or management is applied and an assessment of how the policy/ management modifies the future is carried out.
- **Retrospective intervention evaluation scenarios** answer questions such as: *Have the policy options (e.g. locations of protected areas and level of protection) achieved the anticipated outcomes and goals (e.g. biodiversity enhancement)?* Therefore, this last group of scenarios allows the comparison between the trajectory of a policy or management implemented in the past and scenarios that would have achieved the intended target. Simply put, they are useful for evaluating interventions that have been implemented, comparing them to hypothetical or alternative policies or management practices.

Figure 2. Main types of scenarios that can be developed, according to the objective of scenario builders and users (Biodiversa+ 2020; Modified after: IPBES, 2016a). In exploratory scenarios, the dashed lines represent different plausible futures, often based on storylines. In target-seeking scenarios, the rhombus represents an agreed-upon future target and the coloured dashed lines indicate scenarios that provide alternative pathways for reaching this target. In policy/management-screening scenarios, the dashed lines represent various policy options under consideration. In retrospective policy evaluation, the observed trajectory of a policy implemented in the past (black line) is compared to scenarios that would have achieved the intended target (dashed line)

To develop LENSES strategic roadmaps, we will in general use a combination of exploratory and target-seeking, although we may also consider policy-management screening scenarios.

1.2.3 Strategic roadmaps

In its simplest form, a **roadmap** is a set of interventions defined along a certain timeline. A **strategic roadmap** uses scenario methodology to place these interventions in time to reach a certain vision (desirable future), and considers barriers, risks, and power differences between involved sectors.

These interventions are bundled into clear pathways. In our visioning approach, the exploration of the different sets of actions including the potential trade-offs and synergies among them, comprises the sets of pathways that are required to reach the different visions.

These pathways shall integrate: i) a set of related actions, i.e., policies and norms, behavioral changes, infrastructures (grey, green or hybrid), governance arrangements, etc.; ii) analysis of potential trade-offs between different domains when implementing each pathway; and iii), when clearly identified, potential political or economic barriers hampering the implementation of the key actions and/or reducing their effectiveness.

As a final step, the planned integration of the visioning exercise with the PSDM approach shall allow to combine these pathways with quantitative scenarios for some key variables, thus allowing to estimate the potential effectiveness of each pathway.

1.3. Why a participatory visioning process for prosperous Nexus communities?

Nexus systems are highly complex, which makes their management difficult and requires making decisions under uncertain conditions. Conflicts between users of the same resources, or between different stakeholders with different priorities, as well as competing regulations, arise and undermine the potential of the nexus approach for sustainable development and social prosperity. **A Nexus approach to develop scenarios can help providing solutions to these conflicts**, by aiming for a sustainable and fair allocation of resources, fostering a collaborative paradigm, and overcoming sectorial isolation.

LENSES innovates by contextualizing Resilient Nexus Systems and creating a common vision to address chronic stresses and acute shocks in the diverse pilot contexts. In some pilots, this visioning approach will be developed as a core part of the participatory activities. In these pilots, the LENSES Learning and Action Alliances (**LAAs**) **will integrate stakeholders' discussions and knowledge sharing activities into a structured visioning process concluding in the elaboration of transition roadmaps for the management and operationalization of the Water-Food-Ecosystem nexus** in a plausible, realistic, and holistic manner.

The process of visioning prosperous nexus communities **begins with sharing knowledge among stakeholders in a participatory way**, with the final aim of addressing such conflicts. In its most mature form, the process will lead to trust building between competing stakeholders, and eventually, to appropriate resource management. Such is the intention of the LAA environment. LENSES LAAs involve multi-level and multi-scale stakeholders who will produce shared visions and find tangible ways to implement methods and tools through cooperation. The foundation of the co-creation process in the LAA is the development of transformative (visionary) scenarios for resilience building through the integration of explorative models and participatory activities in line with the work of other WPs outputs. **At the pilot level**, this approach will allow knowledge exchange and improve stakeholders' scientific and technical capacities regarding Water-Food-

Ecosystem nexus, as well as a roadmap for their implementation. **At the project level**, LAAs are intended to enable a multiplicity of stakeholders to set-up a collaborative Nexus space across the Mediterranean region, in which more solutions can be socialized, and scaled-up. The reason behind is that LENSES aims at **not only sharing, but actually integrating methods to develop applicable tools/services** for the Nexus.

2. Guidelines for the development of LENSES strategic roadmaps for Nexus future

The visioning exercise follows a common structured approach comprising four phases through a participatory scenario process:

- i) Identifying the key systemic Nexus challenges;
- ii) Developing a vision for a “business-as-usual” future building on a consolidated narrative of present challenges and stakeholders’ perspectives;
- iii) Use of backcasting techniques to identify and think of actions, norms, policies and programs that could potentially connect the consensual visions for desirable futures with the present situation;
- iv) Assessment of LENSES results for consensus building on policy changes and with best potential for reaching the shared visions, information, and investment gaps.

This section presents guidelines that summarise the methodological approach for the development of the strategic roadmaps through these four steps. The application of this methodology is however very flexible and can be tailored to specific requirements and needs from the pilots.

STEP 1: Identifying the key systemic Nexus challenges

This process builds on a **collective understanding of the current situation and the main sectoral and systemic challenges**. This aim is articulated through a number of potential steps, and it is expected to be the core part of the initial workshop with stakeholders.

STEP 1.1: Problem framing

The process starts with the characterisation of the current situation of the pilot area, represented in a simplified visual format. To this end, a predefined set of materials such as maps and cards with descriptions of infrastructures, economic activities and resources will be provided by WP2 leader to facilitate discussions. These materials will build upon the information collected through the pilot baseline description and the interviews carried out as initial step of the participatory system dynamic model, if available.

Such visual representation provides an opportunity for better understanding the landscape from the perspectives of the different domains and facilitates a deeper discussion of key issues among stakeholders within and across sectors. While this step is largely going to be implemented during workshop 1, it may be presented during workshop 2 as a starting point to engage stakeholders in the exercise, especially in case new stakeholders join in the workshop 2.

As part of the activity, it is suggested to open a discussion where participants can state the main sectoral challenges they identify. This can be done in an oral format, or in a written format:

- **Oral format:** around ten minutes asking in plenary about the main challenges they encounter. Some examples (from the same pilot area or from different case studies) can be provided to facilitate and initiate the process. The facilitator or another person of the organizing team needs to write down all the proposed problems, in a way that can be read by all participants (in a big screen or in a big piece of paper or on a board).
- **Written/ participatory mapping format:** providing each participant with sticky-notes or cards, so that they can write one problem in each sticky-note or choose it from the set of cards. In a second step, participants stick their notes on a big white paper, on the wall or on a blackboard. Alternatively, they place them into a map. In a third step, the facilitator reads to the audience each sticky-note, and groups them by similarity. Some more time can be provided at the end for participants to make oral proposals of additional problems.

STEP 1.2: Prioritisation of the main Nexus challenges

A second step consist in the prioritization of the problems. This can be general or by topic (a prioritization of Water-related problems, of Ecosystems-related problems, of Food-related problems, and of Climate Adaptation and Mitigation related problems). It is important to explain to the participants the criteria or reasons they need to follow in the prioritization, as well as define the challenges collectively (defined first by the analysts but also discussed with the stakeholders at this stage). It is needed to know the reasons behind the prioritization. This can be performed orally or in a written format:

- **Orally:** the facilitator asks for votes for each problem, one by one, and a person from the team writes down the votes for each problem.
- **Written:** each participant can provide a certain number of votes to each problem. They can stand up and stick their votes (stickers) to the most relevant problems.

Once the voting has taken place, the facilitator can read the prioritization of the problems, the ranking of problems with the number of votes. Then, an open discussion can be proposed, to find consensus about: a) the reasons for the prioritization; b) the degree of agreement or disagreement between participants; c) bring up specific problems which have been underlooked but are important, and viceversa.

STEP 1.3: Deduction of the most important Nexus objectives from the main challenges

Following the previous exercise, it may be decided to conclude identifying a set of the most important objectives for the participants towards a more resilient Nexus in the pilot area. Whenever possible, the facilitators will consider the main Domain Objectives defined for each pilot as part of the PSDM preliminary activities.

The identification of the objectives or aims of the participants can be done in a more complex or straightforward format:

- The longest and more complex method would be to follow the same steps of the previous point, just changing “challenges” by “objectives”.
- In a more straightforward way, the facilitator, based on the discussions of point 1, can directly propose the objectives that have been considered more important by the participants.

An open discussion can be proposed to the participants to know the level of agreement with the proposed objectives, any additional objective to be included, and any other consideration. This can take between 10-30 minutes (depending on the chosen method).

STEP 1.4: Prioritization of the objectives

The objective of this step is to finalize with the minimum number of problems and objectives to work with. The LENSES team can choose to work with a certain number of problems and objectives in general in the Pilot area or with a certain number of problems by topic (Water, Ecosystems, Food, Climate Adaptation and Mitigation). In the first case, we propose to work with between 2-5 problems and objectives; and in the second case, with 1-3 problems and objectives by topic.

STEP 2. Defining the “Business as Usual” (BAU) scenario

The business as usual scenario (BAU scenario) summarises a series of changes in key Nexus indicators that are likely to happen if current policies and ‘boundary conditions’ continue. Changes are represented visually by adding or changing existing elements on the map using the same set of cards prepared for the previous step. Next to the foreseen changes, stakeholders will also list along a timeline what actions are expected to take place and by when.

Our recommendation is that organizers start this activity by presenting the main challenges related to the sustainability of the NEXUS between Water, Ecosystems and Food, using the result from previous workshops and participatory activities. If available, results from the Climate Risk Assessment should also be added to this presentation as a key pressure affecting the system, i.e., by threatening water security, level of provision of ecosystem services and food security.

The following activities are recommended for the elaboration of the BAU scenario:

STEP 2.1: Participatory mapping of key drivers

Once we have stated the main challenges and objectives of concern of the pilot for the WEF nexus, the next step is to define a business-as-usual scenario for a mid-term future. The “business as usual” can be defined as “the most probable future based on the current knowledge and on an agreement between participants in its design, which follows the current trends.

Previously to the participatory activity, the organizing team will define the temporal timeframe that can be used in the next steps, or the team can decide to involve the participants in its definition. As another option, the organizing team can propose a temporal horizon to the participants, and based on their reaction, change, or adapt it accordingly. The organizing team can also make it totally open and try to find a consensus between the participants. The temporal time frame is the year that can be used to imagine, to visualize the scenarios and the visions. It can be 2030, 2040, 2100... Since there are many EU-wide relevant policies (e.g., EU Green

Deal, Climate neutrality, Farm2Fork) that have defined clear targets for 2050 linked to their main objectives, this time horizon is recommended as a basis for the elaboration of the BAU scenario as well as for the visions.

For the development of this activity, it is recommended to use the same materials (i.e., a map and a customised set of cards comprising key resources, socioeconomic activities, ecosystem services, pressures, and impacts) that were used in the previous phase for the definition of the systemic challenges.

The first step is the definition of the key drivers. For the design of this activity, it is useful to differentiate between the technological, social, political, economic and environmental drivers of change (using a set of cards and the map representing the pilot area). The central activity shall pivot around participants (representing all the Nexus domains) defining how they imagine the pilot area in the future. To this aim, the attendants shall be asked to think over the expected evolution of the Domain Objectives and main systemic challenges in the future, i.e., describing how they think these will be. On top of this, they will be asked to explain the reason behind these appreciations, i.e., the drivers of change that will define that future.

As a support activity, participants can be asked to develop a discussion explaining the history of the pilot area concerning the WEF nexus issues. The objective of this step is to identify the drivers of change with the highest influence in the past. A good way of doing it is by differentiating between the technological, social, political, economic, and environmental drivers of change.

A timeline can be drawn in the wall, so that participants can add the main drivers of change, the key changes that took place, the disruptive situations (e.g. the approval of a law, the occurrence of a natural or human-driven disaster, the execution of a building, the introduction of a new technology), etc.

STEP 2.2: Business as Usual scenario

The activity will conclude with a recapitulation of the BAU scenario from the perspective of the WEF domains, by identifying how the main Nexus challenges extend over time and reaching a consensus on how the future may look like under current drivers (e.g., climate change) and existing political and economic conditions. This exercise will build on the Nexus resilient qualities and Nexus indicators (details are provided in the D4.1) as means to align these BAU scenarios with the PSDM approach.

The result of this exercise shall be compiled as a narrative explaining the expected status for some key indicators representative of the WEF Nexus and the key drivers that may explain this future status if no meaningful changes are made in current policies implementation and societal behaviour.

STEP 3: Develop the shared vision

It is recommended to carry out this step in conjunction with step 2 in a single workshop, since the development of the shared vision may benefit from the previous consolidation of the BAU scenario.

The identification of desired future states of the Nexus system should build on the ideation of audacious goals, to be coupled with a reflection on a balance for the desired futures.

STEP 3.1: Participatory mapping of objectives: seeking shared value

Participants must define how they would like the WEF Nexus to consolidate in the pilot area in the mid-term future. The defined “objectives” should have a desired state in the temporal frame. For example, it could be

that the groundwater level has stabilized or recovered, that the agricultural production has increased its quality and value, that pollution decreased, and so on.

For this exercise, the facilitator can write on a screen or on a big paper the different objectives set in previous steps, and ask the participants about their preferred state in the temporal frame. Discussion between participants should be encouraged, and the consensus should be sought. In case a consensus cannot be reached, the two most different desired states can be defined and used for the next step. This exercise is much easier to be performed in small groups.

If the time allocated for the exercise is enough, after the consensus has been reached, each group should expose to the other groups in a plenary session their decision. In this case, an agreement between all the groups should be achieved. For supporting this activity, the facilitator can write (on a screen or on a big paper) the defined states for each objective by each group, trying to define for a common value for each objective.

STEP 3.2: Connecting the future to the present (initial step)

As indicated earlier, the concept of 'visions' is closely linked to a back-casting approach for the development of scenarios, although the linkages between the vision and the current state may also be supported by forward planning methods.

To start building these connections, it is recommended to design a specific activity where the workshop participants are asked to identify potential actions that may favor the consecution of the desired vision for a specific domain. These actions may comprise new policies or rules, changes to ensure that existing policies are effectively implemented, the construction or recovery of relevant grey or green infrastructure or novel governance settings.

As a follow up step, these actions will be bundled accordingly to the specific systemic Nexus challenges they are addressing and potential trade-offs from their adoption or implementation will be investigated within the group.

STEP 4: Set the strategic roadmap to reach Nexus resilience

It is recommended that a specific workshop is organized to run through the exercises included in this final step, where the focus will be on developing the strategic roadmaps where the visions of "desirable futures" are linked with their corresponding pathways. Unlike the BAU that continues existing policies and directions, any desired future starts from clear, ambitious but realistic visions of what should be achieved. The rationale for exploring different desirable visions is that stakeholders have a wide range of preferences, values, and world views which make it difficult for everyone to agree on one single desired future. Typically, these divergent values and preferences manifest in difficult trade-offs that need to be weighted. Such trade-offs create critical branching points, where a choice of a particular option results in alternative pathways. For example, developing large scale water infrastructure vs. small scale nature-based solutions may lead to alternative pathways.

STEP 4.1: Connecting the future to the present (Narratives)

This step will build on the results from the previous workshop, e.g., initial identification of actions to be included in the pathways. Based on the desired future (vision), each group will work under a different

exploratory scenario. This means that the participants should know that in the defined time frame (e.g. 2050), the objective has been reached (e.g., groundwater levels and dependent wetlands have been recovered). Then, based on the scenario they are working on, they need to propose what political and private initiatives should have taken place along time, to reach the objective. A timeline shall be used to facilitate this process. For example, participants can propose that in the first years, the government has to provide incentives like subsidies to change to a new particular technology, and in the last years the government has to set fines to all those that do not use the particular technology. The objective of this step is to define a set of practical interventions, which can be used to define a roadmap of interventions along time.

If there is enough time, each group should present their results to the other groups, in a plenary session. Time should be devoted to allow discussion and question and answer from participants of different groups. Each group can define a representative (a speaker) to present their results.

STEP 4.2: Connecting the future to the present (Simulations)

In order to analyse the feasibility of the visions and linked pathways, LENSES is exploring a novel approach that integrates this visioning approach with the development of PSDM for pilot areas. To test the robustness of the selected pathways, it is beneficial to contrast them against quantitative data to be produced by the model as well as contrasting external circumstances (e.g. extreme versus moderate climate change scenarios). As part of this workshop some simulations using the PSDM can be represented in real time, to better illustrate the results of applying the interventions included in the pathways. This exercise allows to analyse whether the main proposed actions are expected to move the system towards the desired vision or whether there are key barriers or large trade-offs that may jeopardise the achievement of the vision.

This methodology has a high potential to produce pathways that integrate the visions from the local and regional stakeholders (i.e., norms, perceptions, beliefs, and values) and are validated and tuned up with quantitative data that explore the feasibility of these pathways based on the PSDM specifically developed for the pilot.

STEP 4.3: Drafting the strategic roadmap

After the workshop, information has been collected to support the production of a **strategic roadmap** for the pilot area. This strategic roadmap shall entail the common interventions proposed by the different groups (each of them working in a different future scenario) and strongly take into consideration the results from the Political Economy Analysis (PEA) undertaken within the frame of WP3. Moreover, these pathways can be completed and/or adapted based on the simulations performed through the PSDM for the pilot.

This integration of methods enables to produce a) feasible pathways with a high internal coherence, since potential tradeoffs will be clearly elucidated; and b) pathways defining a set of selected interventions presenting higher levels or resilience, because they are supposed to be useful under the different possible futures.

3. Application of the guidelines for the design of the strategic roadmaps

The guidelines presented in section 2 have set the ground for the application of the visioning approach by the LENSES pilots by explaining the key concepts of the process and defining the steps to be considered.

It is necessary to apply this methodology through participatory workshops where several stakeholders representing all the WEF Nexus sectors are properly represented. Ideally, the process have taken place through three dedicated workshops although the activities could be accommodated into two or four workshops (see D2.2 for the description of the participatory activities conducted in each pilot).

The guidelines provide basic information, and the pilot leaders have prepared a more detailed design for the organisation of the workshops and related participatory activities, since the process is flexible and can be adapted to the specific needs and objectives of each pilot. To this aim, specific support has been provided by WP2 leader (Ecoadapt) and by WP4 leader (IRSA) to define the concrete activities to be conducted in each workshop and help to analyse the information and reflect about the process.

The participatory scenario planning process have been undertaken in some pilots although not in all of them (similarly to other LENSES methods). In particular, the method has been fully implemented for the Doñana pilot (see section 4) and partially implemented for the Menemen and Pinios pilots, where some aspects of the scenario planning have been integrated with the PEA analysis to identify potential policy recommendations that support a wider adoption of the Nexus approach in policy development (see sections 5 and 6, respectively).

4. Doñana pilot: policy recommendations for the implementation of a Nexus strategic roadmap

From the start of LENSES, Doñana has largely been on the spotlight due to the extended concern of the deterioration of its marshlands and wetlands, and the related affection to the conservation of European migratory birds' populations (see examples from [Le Monde](#), [The Guardian](#), [Der Spiegel](#), [El País](#), [Reuters](#)). In this period, several policy initiatives, plans and measures have been applied (see chapter 4.4) and the participatory work performed within the project has enabled to analyse and assess from a Nexus perspective the selection, prioritisation and implementation potential of these policy measures.

This section elaborates the narrative towards a resilient Doñana region using a Nexus approach and provides key policy recommendations to support an effective design and implementation of a strategic roadmap that builds on the actions already in place. For this, we have applied the four methodological steps of the LENSES method for participatory scenario planning: 1) Identification of key systemic nexus challenges; 2) Definition of the 'business as usual' scenario; 3) Development of a shared vision; and 4) Contribution to a strategic roadmap to reach Nexus resilience.

4.1. Identification of the key systemic Nexus challenges

This activity builds on the work undertaken within WP4 for the elaboration of the Causal Loop Diagram (CLD) and the Participatory System Dynamics Model (PSDM), which is more broadly reported within D4.1 and D4.2.

In terms of **problem framing**, there is a broad consensus that the main problem that Doñana area faces is the (increasing) lack of water resources to make high value-added agricultural activity compatible with the conservation and protection of the region's water ecosystems (marshes, lagoons and coastal wetlands).

Soft fruit crops and rice cultivation require high investments, so the lack of water resources for irrigation is generating very important tensions between farmers whose livelihoods are threatened, as well as companies that run the risk of not being able to recover their investment. This concern is especially present because surface water allocation has been largely reduced in recent irrigation campaigns, both in the Guadalquivir and in the neighbouring Tinto-Odiel-Piedras water districts. Both have seen their allocations reduced sharply in recent irrigation campaigns within the Doñana region, not being able to irrigate the entire cultivated area or being forced to cut the production cycle of some crops, especially strawberries. In the berry production area surrounding the Doñana Natural and National Parks, irrigation allocations have not yet been reduced, although producers know that these reductions may occur in the short term because the aquifer is in a situation of overexploitation and the administration may approve an annual plan of extractions that implies less availability of water per hectare of irrigated land with rights.

Despite the broad consensus on the risk of resource scarcity, disagreements have been detected regarding the causes of the risk. While several stakeholders point out to the lack of an effective mid-term management strategy and to the reduction of available resources due to climate change, many farmers and producers consider that there are sufficient resources for everyone and justify the problem to a lack of new infrastructure for water storage and distribution, - "*The problem is not drought: there is water, but there is no investment in the necessary infrastructure to reach farmers, and it ends up being lost in the sea*" -, other producers put the focus on the "*uncontrolled*" growth of water demand and needs in recent years that has

been supported from public administrations. For example, several farmers were particularly critical on this point, stressing the lack of confidence of the sector in the national and regional public administrations, since "*the administration is not on the ground and does not know what is happening and what we irrigators need*".

On the other hand, Doñana biodiversity is seriously threatened by the reduction of freshwater contributions due to anthropogenic and climatic pressures, mainly competition with irrigated agriculture and droughts. Water-dependent species are being affected by the inadequate conservation status of related habitats while reduced soil moisture is affecting ecological functioning of several key habitats. Some of the interviewees agreed that "*Doñana ecosystems have been so severely transformed and impacted that reverting to the original conditions is no longer possible without radical changes in how the water resources are used*", that are not under consideration because these would entail massive implications for the local socioeconomic system.

The **Nexus challenges** have been selected among the most central elements in the CLD while aiming to adopt a systemic approach. These have been summarized as:

- Ground and surface water resources have been reduced significantly due to droughts and over-irrigation (climate change- hydrologic extremes).
- The marshlands of Doñana and the high-value irrigated agriculture in the pilot area under threat.

In order to address these challenges, **sectoral objectives** have been defined as:

- a) WATER: increase efficiency in water use for irrigation, and support a clear strategy for water allocation among competing sectors
- b) ECOSYSTEMS: increase the annual water flow to the marshlands, support implementation of NBSs that favour biodiversity conservation
- c) FOOD: increase drought resilience of the agricultural sector

In addition, the CLD has been analysed to detect potential **Nexus leverage points**, i.e. elements in the system that can accelerate the impacts of policy interventions for addressing the above-mentioned nexus challenges. These are characterized by several direct and indirect connections and have been defined as:

- Recovery of groundwater levels linked to the reduction of unauthorized groundwater abstraction
- Conservation of marshlands and wetlands ecosystems
- Breeding areas for migratory birds and biodiversity protection
- Increase of farmers' environmental and risk awareness

The decrease in the groundwater levels may lead to a reduction in water allocation to irrigation (in particular to the berry production area) while it is causing the degradation of different ecological resources, i.e. the temporary lagoons and the wetlands. This downfall is connected to the overexploitation of the aquifers (officially declared) and the reduction of the groundwater level is also negatively affecting the Doñana marshland ecosystem state due to the limited contributions of groundwater to the baseflow of La Rocina and El Partido streams (main tributaries from the West) and to the area known as "Ecotono norte" located at the north of the marshlands. This situation is closely connected to the unauthorized groundwater abstraction, that is being addressed by enhanced programs for monitoring and reporting, and for increasing farmers' and society environmental awareness.

The appropriate conservation of the ecosystem strongly affects biodiversity protection with specific reference to the wintering and breeding areas for migratory birds, which in turn relates the problems of Doñana to the European scale because it has been proved that survival and reproduction rates for these birds reduce when wintering and breeding conditions are not adequate. The main element affecting these variables is the rainfall and the key points of intervention are the conservation of the groundwater level and the increase of the Guadiamar contribution to the marshland.

Finally, farmers' environmental awareness could play a key role for the sustainable management of the WEF Nexus, although it has been determined that, to be effective, any policy intervention aiming at increasing the farmers' environmental and risk awareness should account for the need to keep the farmers' income at a satisfactory level.

4.2. Defining the “Business as Usual” (BAU) scenario

The BAU scenario has been defined as the expected situation if no effective action is taken to reduce existing issues, and water availability is further limited by climate change through reduced rainfall, and most importantly, longer and more intense drought periods.

Unfortunately, the region is currently suffering the most severe drought episode ever recorded which is leading to a high tension in the full WEF Nexus system. As shown in [Figure 3](#), there is a clear negative trend in the annual average rainfall for the last 50 years. Drought periods (depicted as yellow boxes) are often not longer than 3-5 years in the Mediterranean climatic context. However, current drought period (i.e., not including any wet year) is already lasting 12 years, including some very dry years. Moreover, average monthly temperature for the year 2022/23 is more than two degrees over the average of the former 40 years.

Figure 3. Evolution of annual rainfall in Doñana and determination of drought periods. Source: CHG (2023b) and EBD data – ‘Palacio de Doñana’ station

When stakeholders were confronted with the elaboration of the BAU scenario, it was argued that current situation can somehow be considered as a good representation, since status of water bodies, water availability for irrigated agriculture, rainfed farming and conservation of protected habitats and species are

being largely affected and impacted. The climate change is here and their effects can be measured and observed: “we do not need to imagine how the future could be”.

The BAU scenario has been developed through the characterisation and analysis of the four main leverage points that related to the main Nexus objectives.

a) Recovery of groundwater levels linked to the reduction of unauthorized groundwater abstraction

Groundwater levels in the Almonte-Marismas aquifer have been monitored by the Guadalquivir river basin authority (CHG) since 1995, when a large network of piezometers was consolidated. In the last monitoring campaign (hydrological year 2022/23) a total of 261 points were measured and analysed to assess the status of 16 sectors in which the aquifer is broken down (CHG, 2024). An indicator (known as le) is used to monitor the evolution of these sectors, characterized as:

$le = 1$	Maximum measured levels.
$0.5 < le < 1$	Normal situation
$0.3 < le < 0.5$	Pre-alert
$0.15 < le < 0.3$	Alert
$0 < le < 0.15$	Alarm
$le = 0$	Minimum measured level

The assessment shows an overall value of 0.24, with 3 sectors in ‘pre-alert’ situation, another 3 sectors in ‘alert’ and 10 sectors assessed as under ‘alarm’ status. In 11 out of the 16 sectors, the observed status is significantly below the expected situation according to the annual precipitation and recharge.

As part of the annual report, the Water Authority states that “the present degree and mode of exploitation of groundwater resources compromises its good status and that of the dependent terrestrial ecosystems”, therefore making the link between groundwater overexploitation and wetlands conservation.

Figure 4 shows how groundwater depletion has led to the formation, since the early 1980s, of two large cones of piezometric depression which are producing a decrease in the flow of the La Rocina stream into the marshlands. The figure integrates the official maps with the evolution of piezometric levels over time with the spatial distribution of intensive irrigated areas (mainly greenhouses, citrus and fruit trees) using groundwater. Both cones accumulate a reduction in the piezometric levels of more than fifteen metres and tend to connect with each other. This situation has led to the disappearance of seeps and wetlands along the northern boundary of the marsh (CHG 2022).

Illegal irrigation is one of the key drivers behind the overexploitation of the aquifer. According to the analysis performed in (Carmona et al, 2024) for the 2023/24 irrigation campaign in the berry production area within the Guadalquivir basin (i.e., Rocina groundwater body), overall groundwater abstraction was 37.8 hm^3 whereas average groundwater recharge is estimated as 28.8 hm^3 . This implies an over-abstraction of 9.0 hm^3 of which a total of 6 hm^3 corresponds to irrigation under potentially illegal conditions for not having a water use permit. In addition, at least a similar volume is estimated to be used as an over-abstraction from legal farms over the maximum allowed volume per hectare. This provides a clear example of how the restriction of the illegal use of water for irrigation could lead to a more sustainable management of the resources. As a side issue, in the interviews conducted with an Association of Farm Workers of the province of Huelva, as well as in the focus group with berry farmers, the relationship between illegal irrigation and the vulnerability of temporary farm workers was highlighted. It was claimed that labour conditions in many of these illegal farms are not monitored by public administrations on the same level as they are for legal farms.

Figure 4. Impact of groundwater depletion on the evolution of piezometric levels of the Almonte-Marismas aquifer. Source: (CHG 2023 – ‘Doñana factsheet’) and own elaboration. Dashed yellow lines show the position of the piezometric depressions.

In terms of expected trends, although water abstractions are stable in last years, climate change will also affect the soil water balance. Considerable reductions in recharge values to aquifers and groundwater bodies are expected with respect to current values (see [Table 1](#)), ranging from a reduction of 8.5% for the optimistic scenario (RCP4.5) to 18.5% for the pessimistic scenario (RCP8.5).

Table 1. Groundwater recharge reduction at Almonte-Marismas aquifer for the horizon 2039 (taken from CHG (2023))

Groundwater body	RCP4.5 (% change)	RCP 8.5 (% change).
Almonte	-8,2	-17,6
Marismas	-9,0	-18,8
Marismas de Doñana	-9,0	-17,7
Manto Eólico de Doñana	-8,0	-18,4
La Rocina	-8,1	-18,5

In terms of water quality, there are two main causes of surface and groundwater pollution in the Doñana region: i) urban and industrial discharges; and ii) fertilisers and other pollutants used in agriculture.

Annual monitoring reports from the Water Authorities show high values of pollutants (e.g., ammonium, nitrites) in the Partido and Rocina streams, which frequently reach values corresponding to poor chemical status. Groundwater bodies where the intensive agriculture takes place are mostly in bad ecological status (e.g., Almonte and Condado groundwater bodies). La Rocina groundwater body is overall declared in good status although measurements in most of the areas that are closer to the greenhouses (e.g., Rocina, La Cañada, Don Gil and Moriana streams) show values in nitrates concentration between 54 and 65 mg/l, way over the legal threshold of 35 mg/l (CHG, 2023b).

A compilation of studies (WWF, 2024a) demonstrates that *“there are significant concentrations of anti-inflammatory drugs, antibiotics and other pharmaceutical products in the water and sediments of the Rocina and Partido streams and Guadiamar river, which often exceed the limits that generate toxic effects in animals and plants”*. It has also been noticed the presence of a high genetic diversity of Escherichia coli bacteria in the northwest area of the marshes (Paredes et al., 2021).

b) Conservation of marshlands and wetlands ecosystems

Doñana is mainly a freshwater wetland, dependent on rainfall, and inflows from rivers and temporary streams, which in turn are dependent on the water contributions from the aquifer.

Therefore, the adequate conservation of its main ecosystems relates to rainfall and groundwater levels.

A recent research article (Green et al, 2023) provides a compilation of scientific evidence over the impacts on the natural ecosystems (marshlands, dune ponds or the ecotone, as well as terrestrial vegetation) due to groundwater drawdowns and deterioration of water quality.

Doñana National Park includes over 3,000 temporary ponds and some lagoons which are designated as a priority habitat according to the EU Habitats Directive (i.e., HCI 3170). A specific assessment using remote sensing to delineate these habitats over time (de Felipe et al, 2023) has determined that a 59% of the ponds within this area have completely dried out, i.e., these have not been flooded at least after 2013. The study demonstrates a statistically significant relationship between the deterioration of ponds and the increase in groundwater abstraction due to the expansion of berry cultivation, even after discounting the effects which can be related to climate change. Beyond agricultural abstractions, this area is also affected by the use of groundwater resources to supply the water demand of the Matalascañas site, a touristis place by the sea located a few kilometres away. The normal population is below 3,000 inhabitants, but this

number skyrockets to a regular population of more than 150,000 inhabitants in summer, reaching 300,000 people in some of the weekends.

The EBD recently drafted a report to inform the Doñana Participatory Board about the current status of the Doñana wetlands (EBD, 2023), which illustrates the actual status of many of these ponds, which have been fully desiccated and invaded by vegetation formations that are typical of soils with low moisture content² (see [Figure 5](#)).

Figure 5. Example of changes derived from the desiccation of the Doñana's temporary lagoons – 'Laguna del Moral'. Source: extracted from (EBD, 2023)

As another example, the Santa Olalla lagoon, which is the largest permanent lagoon in Doñana, has completely dried up in the last two summer period (i.e., 2022 and 2023). Although this lagoon has desiccated before under strong drought periods, this is the first time this situation produces two years in a row in the last 50 years, i.e., since there is a continuous monitoring of the lagoon flooded area.

These ponds and lagoons constitute one of the habitats with higher biodiversity in Doñana, and their deterioration is directly affecting the structural and functional biodiversity of the area. As reported in (EBD, 2023), populations of amphibians, reptiles (e.g., Galapagos), insects (e.g., odonatan), fishes (e.g., eels) and aquatic plants are being severely impacted.

The extension of the annual flooded area in these habitats is regularly monitored by the CHG (see [Figure 6](#)), and constitutes a valid indirect indicator for monitoring the conservation of wetlands in our BAU scenario. The current trend shows a statistically significant decrease in the evolution of the annual flooded area.

² Scrublands dominated by *Halimium halimifolium*, accompanied by *Cistus salvifolius* and *Cistus libanotis*, and locally known as 'monte blanco'

Figure 6. Evolution of the flooded area in Doñana's ponds and lagoons (CHG, 2023b)

The marshlands status has been monitored by some authors through the maximum annual flooded area. However, other authors (see Green et al, 2023) have demonstrated that the variation in the mean hydroperiod (i.e. average length of time flooded averaged across the marsh area) is a more reliable indicator to measure a good ecological status of the marshlands, as it related to the existence of good conditions for the delivery of the main ecological functions of these ecosystems.

Figure 7 (Díaz Delgado, 2024) synthetises the change in hydroperiod within the marshes within the period from 1974 to 2021. It is clearly observed how negative trends are more extended than positive trends, which are often related to changes in marshes flooding dynamics due to sedimentation.

Figure 7. Evolution of the trend in annual flooded areas of the marshlands in 1974-2021 (extracted from Green et al, 2023)

Nevertheless, overall annual flooded area remains a strong indicator of the changes in the annual marshes status as a consequence of rainfall variability and droughts. Figure 8 on the next page, provides an example of the maximum extension of the marshes in a wet winter within a rainy period in comparison with the 2023/24 winter, where a minimum part of the marshes were flooded.

Figure 8. Comparison of the extension of flooded marshlands on a wet year (20,800 ha) against dry conditions (200 ha in winter 2023/24) within the Doñana National Park.

Source: own elaboration using Landsat 8 and Sentinel 2 satellite images

c) Breeding areas for migratory birds and biodiversity protection

According to the [data published by the Spanish Ministry of Environment](#), there are currently 20 species of freshwater fish, 11 of amphibians, 21 of reptiles, 37 of non-marine mammals and 360 birds, of which 127 breed regularly in the Park. Moreover, more than 1,500 plant species have been identified in the Doñana natural area. However, this biodiversity is following a negative trend due to several threats, e.g., invasive species, climatic changes, deterioration of freshwater ecosystems, and lack of appropriate conditions in freshwater habitats for breeding.

The wetland is widely recognized as a natural area of international environmental value as a wintering area, migratory passage and breeding area for the aquatic birdlife. Its geographical location, bridging between three different biogeographical regions (European, African and Macaronesian) and two continents within the largest Palearctic region, makes the Doñana marshes a place of prime importance for migratory waterfowl species.

The international census of wintering birds in wetlands is coordinated by Wetlands International and carried out in 143 countries during the months of January and February. In Doñana, this census is undertaken by the Doñana’s Biological Station (EBD) to estimate the number of birds that live in the wetland during their wintering by collecting data through aerial, terrestrial and roosting census. The evolution of this indicator provides a clear indication of the existing trend (see [Figure 9](#)). This is also a reliable proxy for waterfowl conservation status across Europe since wintering conditions directly affect to their reproduction and survival rates after migration to their northern distribution areas. In 2024, the number of wintering birds reached a minimum value within the full historical series, way below average recorded values.

Figure 9. Annual number of annual wintering birds in Doñana wetlands between 2001 and 2014. Source: international census of wintering birds – data compiled by the EBD

d) Increase of farmers' environmental and risk awareness

Water availability is perceived as farmers as their main risk for the sustainability of their activity. The declaration of an emergency situation as part of the drought plan approved by the CHG, has derived in water use limitations for the agricultural sector, as human consumption and industrial uses have a preference according to the Water Law. This has made evident for irrigated agriculture dependent on surface water, which are managed by the Water Authority. As a clear example, [Figure 10](#) graphically illustrates and explains the magnitude of water availability reductions for the rice production around Doñana. The BAU considers that this kind of situations will get more frequent because of climate change.

Groundwater-dependent agriculture has not suffered similar restrictions because annual water use plans for the groundwater bodies declared in bad quantitative status have yet not entered into place, as we are now within a moratorium period until central groundwater users' communities (CUAS) are set up for each body. However, it is expected that in the near future, water use per hectare will be limited when groundwater recharge is estimated below a threshold volume that enables a sustainable management of groundwater resources.

The illegal use and abstraction of groundwater is also perceived as an additional risk factor. This practice is considered as a factor of unfair competition, and contributes to the increase of operating costs due to the need to deepen boreholes and because pumped water has higher amounts of sand and suspended solids. There is recognition that important efforts are being made by the CHG and the State Attorney General's Office to reduce the area of illegal irrigation, but farmers complain about how slow the process is. In general, eradicating bad practices in the sector is considered a priority to reduce the level of risk. In any case some reports (WWF, 2019; Carmona et al, 2024) show that there is a trend towards the reduction of illegal water use in farming.

Moreover, the producers perceive that, at present, the critical situation of the Doñana wetlands has created an additional reputational risk for the entire sector of berry production in Huelva. European retailers and supermarkets are starting to look in detail to water challenges in Doñana region since they want to ensure that sustainability in the value chain is not jeopardized, and many EU customers are showing their concern about environmental issues in the area and the possible link with the produce they buy.

Berry producers in general agreed that potential reductions in water availability and reputational risk are the biggest threats to their activity - "*our main objective is to ensure that we can meet our short and medium-term commitments to distributors and supermarkets*". Faced with these risks, they believe that the sector must remain united, and demonstrate the efforts being made in terms of increased efficiency in water consumption and reduction of environmental impact. However, they also complain that adopting these practices (e.g., good management practices) provokes a competitive disadvantage with other production areas outside of the EU (e.g., Northern Africa) where many aspects of the legislation are less strict and demanding.

As a consequence, farmers are concerned about the possibility of safeguarding the current level of high-added value agriculture near Doñana, which is the main socioeconomic activity in the province.

Figure 10. Evolution of rice cultivation near Doñana (2020 – 2023)

The four satellite images were acquired the same day (15th July) of different years, i.e., 2020, 2021, 2022, and 2023.

Areas cultivated with rice can be observed in dark green colour (see 2020 image). Boundaries of the rice paddies are depicted in dark orange.

In 2020, the total cultivated surface accounted for nearly 39,000 hectares, which makes for the largest rice cultivation area across Europe.

In 2021, irrigated area using surface water was cut down by half, whereas in 2022, only one third of the rice paddies were cultivated.

In 2023, there was no rice cultivation, since the irrigators communities decided to sell out their water use rights to other water users. In this year, only a few areas in the West, which use groundwater for irrigating rice crops were cultivated.

Source: own elaboration using Sentinel 2 images from ESA - Copernicus

Finally, main aspects considered in the BAU scenario are summarised within [Figure 11](#), which is labelled as ‘Doñana in crisis’ and defines the expected situation if no effective action takes place, and unfortunately, builds on the current situation for the WEF Nexus.

As part of the interviews undertaken within the participatory process, it was pointed out that "*Doñana is fighting against its own history*" because the land-use planning was conceived on a model focusing on agricultural development in an area with low socio-economic development and in the surroundings of a natural environment of high ecological value that would be preserved.

Time has shown that agricultural and environmental systems are closely interconnected through water resources and cannot be planned and managed separately.

The BAU scenario is characterised by three sectoral challenges linked to specific objectives, with a number of indicators already defined to monitor their status, as summarised in [Table 2](#).

Table 2. Summary of objectives, leverage actions and indicators for the BAU scenario

SECTOR	Key shared challenges and objectives	Leverage actions	Indicators
Water	Good quantitative and qualitative status of water bodies	Recovery of groundwater levels / Reduction of unauthorized groundwater abstraction	Groundwater bodies status indicator (Ie) Monitoring of illegal irrigated area through remote sensing Water quality measurements
Ecosystems	Biodiversity conservation	Conservation of marshlands and wetlands ecosystems Breeding areas for migratory birds and biodiversity protection	Monitoring of the hydroperiod (number of annual days under flooding conditions) Number of wintering birds
Food	Ensuring water availability for irrigated agriculture	Increase of farmers’ environmental and risk awareness	Annual extension of irrigated crops and monitoring of water use

The BAU scenario has been determined by:

- a) Groundwater bodies in bad status, lack of ecological flows in surface water bodies and nos sufficient connections between water bodies
- b) Doñana being in the spotlight as an international example of biodiversity loss and degradation of habitats of high environmental value
- c) Sustainability of a core economic activity (irrigated agriculture) threatened by lack of water availability and reputational risk
- d) Climatic threats (in particular droughts and rainfall reduction) exacerbating increasing pressure over the whole system

Figure 11. Representation of the BAU scenario

4.3. A shared vision: 'Resilient Doñana'

During the participatory process, one of the interviewees concluded that due to the model developed in recent decades and the growing impact of climate change, we must accept that *'the Doñana we knew has been lost and the most we can aspire to is to seek a "Doñana adapted" to the new climatic conditions'*, even for which we will have to implement an ambitious set of measures and plans. Even though we have built the vision for Doñana considering an ideal best case scenario where all core Nexus challenges are sorted out, participants in the workshops agreed that getting back to past conditions is not likely to happen, so novel scenarios need to be drawn up. Sea level rise has been added as an additional climatic threat, since the influence from the Guadalquivir estuary into the marshlands is going to increase in the mid and long term. This will affect to some extent to the characteristics of the wetland since tidal influence is likely to increase and some areas will receive more brackish water.

The vision scenario (see [Figure 12](#)) has been defined as an accelerated evolution from the BAU scenario towards a desired situation where all Nexus components get balanced and main objectives are achieved:

- a) Good status of groundwater and surface water bodies and recovery of the connection between water bodies – in compliance with the goals of the Water Framework Directive. This involves the achievement of a good qualitative and quantitative status for all water bodies, including a recovered connection between groundwater and surface water bodies.

- b) Doñana getting identified as an international example of biodiversity conservation under climate change threats. – in compliance with the Green Deal and the Nature Restoration Law. It implies an adequate conservation of species and habitats, good ecological connection to other natural areas, and the maintenance of the delivery of ecosystem services. As part of the process, the recovery of water inflows from Guadiamar and main streams to the marshlands and the extension of the protected area are key objectives.
- c) Doñana becomes a recognized example of sustainable farming and develops a Doñana branding for farming products supporting biodiversity and territorial sustainability – in alignment with the Farm to Fork strategy. This is defined by the maintenance of the high-value agriculture (or at least a similar socio-economic level) together with i) an efficient and technology-driven use of water in agriculture with high self-management capacity by water users; ii) the extension of good management practices preserving biodiversity; and iii) diversified farming systems including traditional rainfed crops.

Figure 12. Representation of the Doñana vision

4.4. Supporting a strategic roadmap towards a resilient WEF Nexus

The strategic roadmap is a central output of the scenario planning. Its aim is to facilitate and steer the implementation of the necessary measures and processes to move from the BAU scenario towards the desired vision (see [Figure 13](#)). Our approach follows a sequential approach which includes: i) a diagnosis phase (elaboration of the BAU scenario –section 4.3); ii) the identification and prioritisation of solutions (measures); and the elaboration of a plan for the coordinated implementation of these solutions (roadmap).

The identification of solutions builds upon several policy initiatives released in the last couple of years (see section 4.4.1), although these measures have been complemented with other potential actions driven by the private sector. The potential solutions are listed in section 4.4.2. These measures are, however, not clearly interrelated and criteria for their selection and prioritisation are not properly elaborated. To overcome this barrier, we have conducted prioritisation exercises (see section 4.4.3) and a Political-Economy Analysis (PEA) – see section 4.4.4. This process provides some answers to questions related to power relations, barriers, and incentives, or values that can enable or limit the adoption of measures. The key information extracted from these analyses is synthetised in section 4.4.5 through the elicitation of policy recommendations for the development of an integral strategic roadmap towards a ‘resilient Doñana’ region. The elaboration of this roadmap is unfortunately out of the scope of the LENSES project and should be propelled through an integrated and coordinated effort of the public administrations supported by a broad and sustained participatory process.

Figure 13. Sequential steps towards the vision scenario

4.4.1. Governance and policy analysis

The distribution of policy and management competences for water, land use planning, agriculture and environment is complex in the study area.

In terms of water resources, water use planning and monitoring, and water management are in general the responsibility of the Guadalquivir river basin authority (*Confederación Hidrográfica del Guadalquivir - CHG*), which depends on the central government (*Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico - MITERD*). For a small area at the western part of the Almonte-Marismas aquifer which locates within the Tinto-Odiel-Piedras (TOP) river basin, these competences fall into the regional government (*Junta de Andalucía – JA*). This difference is due to the fact that the TOP basin is entirely located within the Andalusia region, while the Guadalquivir hydrographic demarcation extends over some other regions. There is a water transfer already approved from TOP into the Guadalquivir basin for human consumption and irrigation of berries. Municipalities also are partly responsible of water management, in particular for aspects related to urban water uptake and distribution, and to water sanitation and treatment.

The competences related to agriculture and spatial planning fall almost entirely on the regional administration (JA). At state level, the Ministries (MITERD and Agriculture Ministry) carry out some tasks for monitoring, coordination and liaison with European policies and institutions.

Finally, environmental planning and management is also transferred to the regional authority autonomous communities, including the management of protected natural areas. In environmental matters, many management and monitoring tasks are also devolved to the municipalities. The Ministry also carries out overall monitoring, coordination and integration tasks at the European level.

A relevant governance structure is the '[Doñana Participation Council](#)'. This is formed by more than 50 representatives of different institutions and sectors (central government, regional administration, national park management, land owners, municipalities, farmers' unions, scientists, industry, etc.). This is a consultative and non-prescriptive body that convenes once a year and whose main functions are to share information, make recommendations, promote public participation, compile information, and in general, contribute to the objectives stipulated in the declaration of the Doñana Natural Area.

The main instruments underpinning water, agriculture and territorial planning and management are:

- a) The river basin management plans (RBMP) for the 2022-2027 cycle (approved in 2023) for the Guadalquivir and the TOP (CHG, 2023; Junta de Andalucía, 2023b). These documents set out the water use planning and management principles in each river basin district. They estimate water uses and demands, and establish environmental objectives for the achievement of good status of the water bodies. Moreover, the RBMPs include a programme of measures, i.e., a set of actions with an allocated budget to help achieve the objectives of the plan.
- b) The general land use plan for the berry production area (*Plan de Ordenación Territorial del Ámbito de Doñana - POTAD*) approved in December 2003 (Junta de Andalucía, 2003). This plan establishes the criteria for land use planning, including areas compatible with rainfed and irrigated agricultural uses. The POTAD is a regulatory framework whose purpose is to guarantee the preservation of natural resources and the sustainable development of the municipalities near the Doñana Natural Area.
- c) The Special Plan for the management of irrigated areas in the Doñana Forest Crown (*Plan Especial de Ordenación de los Regadíos de la Corona Forestal de Doñana - PEORCFD*) approved in December 2014

(Junta de Andalucía, 2014). The PEORCFD is a regulatory development of the POTAD and sets out the criteria for the delimitation of irrigable agricultural lands, which delineates those areas where irrigated agriculture is compatible with land management. The Plan is also justified by the important role of the agricultural sector in the economy of this area and by the need to guarantee an image of orderly and sustainable development on the markets. The scope of application of the PEORCFD coincides with most of the berry production area.

- d) The new action frameworks for the Doñana area, promoted by MITERD ([Action Framework for Doñana 2022](#), and [Action Framework for the Sustainable Territorial Development of the Area of Influence of the Doñana Natural Area 2023](#)) and the Regional Government of Andalusia ([Action Plan for the Rural Development of the Doñana region 2023](#)), and which bring together many of the measures included in other plans together with new measures favouring social, economic and environmental sustainability for the territorial area of Doñana (described in section 4.2).

4.4.2. Identification of measures

The overall perception – captured through the interviews to key stakeholders – is that the main issues and challenges for the WEF Nexus in the region are not related to a lack of appropriate policies, legislative instruments and/or planning tools for water, environmental or agricultural management. The existing regulation is well aligned with the EU Directives and properly transposes the commitments made by Spain through international and EU treaties (Ramsar Convention, Protection of World Cultural and Natural Heritage, EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2020, etc.).

This section compiles the most relevant measures promoted by the public administrations for the Doñana region and which have been included in strategies and plans already in place.

a) Program of measures for the Guadalquivir RBMP (CHG, 2023)

The measures included in the RBMP for 2022-2027 have a significant focus on the achievement of the environmental objectives imposed by the Water Framework Directive, mainly the achievement quantitative, qualitative and ecological status of the water bodies, with specific references to the Doñana area. The allocated budget for the implementation of measures within the Guadiamar exploitation system reaches 418 M€. This budget is broken down by types of measures in [Table 3](#).

Table 3. Allocated budget for the implementation of measures in the Guadiamar system (RBMP 2022-2027). Source: Own elaboration based on data included in the RBMP.

Type of action	Allocated budget (M€)	Examples of planned measures
1. Compliance with environmental objectives	391	
Conservation and improvement of the structure and functioning of aquatic ecosystems	1	Studies to improve existing knowledge
Improvement of hydrological conditions	1	Improving longitudinal connectivity in rivers
Improvement of morphological conditions	25	Floodplain restoration (Guadiamar river) to improve connectivity to Doñana marshlands

Reduction of diffuse pollution	6	Riverside forest restoration
Reduction of point source pollution	358	Improvement of sanitation networks and wastewater treatment plants
Reduction of water abstraction pressure	558	Purchase of agricultural lands with water rights to reduce water abstractions; change of the location of boreholes for the supply of Matalascañas
2. Knowledge and governance measures	9	Modeling tools; improvement of the groundwater monitoring network (piezometers); support actions to improve governance
3. Satisfying demands by increasing available resources	17	Upgrade of the existing infrastructure to support water transfer from TOP basin
TOTAL	418	

b) Doñana 2022 Plan: hydrological and environmental restoration

In 2022 the MITERD promoted the Doñana Action Framework with the aim of reversing the environmental degradation of the natural environment and recovering its ecological functioning. This framework for action (MITERD, 2022) has a total budget of 356 million euros to undertake a wide range of actions (see [Table 4](#)) aiming at the management of water resources, the conservation and restoration of biodiversity in the area, coastal management of the public maritime-terrestrial domain, the socio-environmental recovery of the territory and the improvement of knowledge.

Table 4. Main measures included in the Doñana 2022 plan. Source: own elaboration based on (MITERD, 2022)

1. Management and administration of the public water domain
1.1 Closure of illegal wells and improvement of governance and guardianship, with strict control of pumping, including remote sensing and remote monitoring of water meters
1.2 Establishment of groundwater user communities in aquifers at risk of not achieving good quantitative or chemical status.
2. Reduction of groundwater abstractions
2.1. Purchase of farmland with water rights for the recovery of water bodies in the area of Doñana
2.2. Decommissioning of wells and consideration of alternative water sources. Substitution of groundwater for surface water through transfer of resources in accordance with Law 10/2018
2.3. Substitution of groundwater by surface water from the El Agrio reservoir
2.4. Reduction of the impact caused by water abstractions for the supply of water to Matalascañas
3. Recovery of surface hydrology
3.1. Recovery of the natural fluvial dynamics of the marshes
3.2. Hydrological-forest restoration of the 'Los Mimbrales' site
3.3. Vegetation and geomorphological restoration of the Arroyo del Partido stream
4. Biodiversity conservation and restoration
4.1. Actions to integrate the objectives of the Water and Nature Directives and other environmental strategies and regulations through Nature-based Solutions (NbS) with an ecosystem approach
4.2. Enhancing ecological connectivity and habitat defragmentation
4.3. Actions to improve habitats of Special Interest
4.4. New integrated LIFE project "Priority actions for the conservation and restoration of Doñana"
4.5. Climate change adaptation call for projects
5. Socio-economic activation of Doñana's region
5.1. Promotion of agri-food products, other goods and services in the Doñana area that promote a sustainable use of resources, especially water resources, to promote sustainable production and a change towards the development of a model in accordance with the environmental values of the area
5.2. Calls for 'Green employment' programme
5.3. Call for Bioeconomy Grants
5.4. Calls for 'Green employment+' programme
5.5. Spanish Business and Biodiversity Initiative (IEEB)

5.6. Support to the recognition of the Sustainability of Nature Tourism in the marine Natura 2000 Network
6. Recovery and naturalisation of the maritime-terrestrial public domain in Doñana and its surroundings
6.1. Delimitation and recovery of the maritime-terrestrial public domain
6.2. Renaturalisation and defence of the maritime-land public domain
7. Improving sanitation and water treatment in the Doñana area
8. Improving knowledge and monitoring
8.1. Support to the Doñana Biological Station (EBD) – CSIC
8.2. Improving knowledge of hydrological processes in Doñana: groundwater and surface water
8.3. Functional model of the aquifers and surface hydrology in the perimeter of the Doñana Forest Crown
8.4. Improvement and automation of the piezometric monitoring network
8.5. Improving the systems and methods for assessing the status of surface water bodies
8.6. Study of the location of sources of chemical pollution in the Guadiamar river basin

c) Doñana 2023 Plan: territorial development

In 2023, MITERD and the Regional Government of Andalusia signed an inter-institutional agreement to collaborate in coordinated actions and guarantee the sustainability of the agricultural, socio-economic and environmental system of Doñana. As part of this agreement, the MITERD has presented the a plan for the sustainable territorial development of the area of influence of the Doñana Natural Area (MITERD, 2023), which complements Action Framework Doñana2022 by incorporating specific actions aimed at strengthening the social and economic dimensions towards territorial sustainability in the area. According to the Ministry's website, this plan "*constitutes a commitment to a territorial project that, while dynamising and intensifying the ecological transition, allows the social and economic conditions of the area to be improved*".

For this purpose, the MITERD has allocated an additional budget of €350 million to be distributed among a wide range of measures (see [Table 5](#)) that are of interest, directly or indirectly, for the region's agro-productive sector.

Table 5. Main measures included in the Action Framework for the Doñana Natural Area 2023.

Source: own elaboration based on (MITERD, 2023)

1. Agri-food sector	
1.1 Diversification of agricultural production	1.1.1 Renaturalisation of areas currently used for agricultural production 1.1.2 New rainfed crops 1.1.3 Conversion towards ecological production models
1.2 Measures to improve the quality and value of agri-food production	1.2.1 Promote the creation of a guarantee brand linked to Doñana 1.2.2 Encourage short marketing cycles for local products 1.2.3 Specific promotion measures
1.4 Additional support measures for the agricultural sector	1.4.1 Support for the rice and cotton sector, improving farming techniques and marketing through the "Doñana Brand" 1.4.2 Support to farmers for the development of initiatives to reduce the generation of non-packaging agricultural plastic waste 1.4.3 Support for the demonstration of best practices in agriculture and livestock
1.6 RD&I in agricultural technologies	1.6.1 Support for RD&I companies in agricultural technologies

	1.6.2 Promotion of digitalisation systems to improve efficiency in the use of water and fertilisers in irrigated agriculture
3. Forestry sector	3.1 Support for the improvement of forest management 3.2 Support to the creation of associations of forest owners to facilitate the implementation of joint management plans 3.3 Support to the modernisation of companies in the sector, promoting their digitalisation 3.5 Support for the development of forestry-related activities 3.6 Forest restoration of degraded land and application of preventive forestry to reduce fire risk
6. Renewable energy and energy efficiency sector	6.2 Promote projects for the integration of renewable energies in agricultural activity
8. Certification - Doñana Brand	
8.1. 'Doñana Biosphere Reserve' brand	8.1.1 Training for the Management Body 8.1.2 Identify companies and producers to carry out an information and awareness-raising process
11. Gender equality	11.1 Specific gender equality actions 11.2 Cross-cutting gender equality actions in the rest of the action lines
12. Training and improving employability	12.1 Training actions in partnership with other actors 12.2 Green job creation 12.3 Development of methodologies for training and improving employability 12.4 Provision of funds to develop a specific sustainability training offer 12.5 Strengthen the Programme for the Promotion of Agricultural Employment (PFEA) 12.6 Extension of the Andalusia Employment Plan to 55 million euros, earmarking 5 million euros for the Doñana area of influence
13. Improving the living conditions and habitability of housing for seasonal farm workers	
13.1 Socio-occupational inclusion of foreign seasonal workers	13.1.1 Prevention and awareness-raising aimed at the population of foreign origin.
13.4 Access to decent accommodation for seasonal workers	13.4.1 Construction and rehabilitation of decent housing for seasonal workers for use during the agricultural campaigns 13.4.2 Specialised intermediation 13.4.3 Shelter-accommodation network 13.4.4 Portable modules with access to drinking water, toilets and electrical charging points (short term)
14. Cultural heritage	14.1.8 Promotion of Doñana as a tourist destination of Landscape Quality

d) Action Plan for Rural Development 2023

As a complement to the Doñana 2023 Action Framework, the Regional Government (JA) has presented a rural development plan (Junta de Andalucía, 2023) with an allocated budget of 728.9 M€ with several measures (see [Table 6](#)).

Table 6. Main measures included in the Rural Development plan. Source: Own elaboration based on (Junta Andalucía, 2023)

Type of action	Allocated budget (M€)	Examples of planned measures
1. Fishing sector	23.5	Management plans for key species; governance measures
2. Water infrastructure	334.8	Waste water treatment plants; sanitation infrastructure; water regulation infrastructure
3. Agricultural and livestock sector	251.5	Support to municipalities through FEAGA and FEADER funds
4. Forest and natural areas	21.3	Restoration of burned areas; habitats restoration; programs against invasive species
5. Doñana Natural Area	96.3	Purchase of the “Veta la Palma” site (72M) and development of specific water management and biodiversity conservation actions; biodiversity conservation programs; wetland restoration actions
6. Land use planning	1.5	Setting up a Technical Office; revision of land use plans (POTAD and PEORCFD)
TOTAL	728.9	

4.3. Prioritisation of measures

The description of the existing measures do not include criteria or specific information (e.g. cost-benefit analysis) to enable a clear prioritization of these measured. An exercise was conducted as part of the second workshop of the pilot (see D2.2 for further explanation) to select central measures to form the skeleton of the strategic roadmap.

The potential measures described within the previous sections were summarized and integrated into a list of 30 measures, including: diversification of agricultural production, technology to improve irrigation efficiency, specific support to forestry/ livestock /industrial sectors, sustainable tourism, Doñana branding, support to renewable energies / IT technologies, improve living conditions of farm workers, closing down of illegal boreholes, improving governance, creation of groundwater users’ communities, purchase of farming sites to reallocate water rights to environmental use, payments for afforestation of farming sites, change location of pumping boreholes to supply Matalascañas site, reconnection of Guadiamar river to the marshlands, NbS and green corridors to improve ecological connectivity, recovery of floodplains, regenerative agriculture and eco-schemes, plans for priority habitats and species, recovery and restoration of river forest areas, improvement of water treatment, substituting groundwater use by surface water use, increasing management capacities of water users, development of improved water infrastructures (collection, use and transport), climate change adaptation plan, purchase of lands with high ecological value to be included into the protected areas, improving coordination between public administrations, environmental education and awareness programmes, and water stewardship programmes.

These measures were printed in small cards included a summarized description of what accompanying actions are envisaged for each measure (see example on the right side) and set into a timeline of priority actions towards an accelerated transition from the BAU scenario into the vision.

The workshop participants selected those actions that have a better balance between efficacy (i.e., capacity to move away from BAU into the sustainability vision) and difficulty (i.e., how likely is that the measures can be implemented under real conditions).

Diversification of agricultural production and improvement of the quality and value of agri-food production

(Conversion to organic production models / New rainfed crops / Encouraging short marketing cycles and promotion measures / Funding of demonstration projects)

The list of priority measures comprises several short-term and mid-term actions that are very much aligned with the main goals identified for the vision (see figure *):

- Goal#1: Achieve the good status of groundwater and surface water bodies
- Goal#2: Doñana gets identified as an international example of biodiversity conservation under climate change threats
- Goal#3: Doñana becomes a recognised example of sustainable farming – setting up of the ‘Doñana Biosphere Reserve’ branding

The main measures – and their key linkages to these goals- are:

a) In the short-term (temporal scope of 2030)

- (1) Improving coordination among public administrations with different competences and acting on different scales [Goal#1, Goal#2, Goal#3]
- (2) The closure of illegal wells and the implementation of a governance program to ensure the effective reduction of illegal farming, leading to a reduction of irrigated surface and groundwater abstractions [Goal#1, Goal#3]
- (3) Setting up of central groundwater users communities, with a broader range of competences to participate and collaborate in the management of the water resources [Goal#1, Goal#3]
- (4) Purchase of farmlands with water rights in order to reduce groundwater abstractions and reallocate these water rights into environmental use [Goal#1]
- (5) Support to the modernization of the agri-food sector, and specific action to promote sustainability practices in intensive agriculture [Goal#3]. Different actions are required depending on the current level of technological development for high-value (e.g., greenhouses) and traditional crops (e.g. rainfed crops)
- (6) Improvement of current water sanitation and water treatment systems, leading to an improvement in water quality of surface water bodies [Goal#1, Goal#2]

Other relevant measures although assigned with a lesser priority are:

- relocation of the wells that supply water to Matalascañas touristic site to other areas where water abstractions have less impact on the coastal lagoons
- development of water stewardship programmes (through public-private collaboration)
- specific programs for biodiversity monitoring and conservation
- a consolidated program for environmental awareness and environmental education
- actions for improving working and living conditions of temporary workers in the farming sector
- the elaboration of a multi-sectoral climate change adaptation plan at a regional scale

b) *In the mid-term (temporal scope of 2040)*

- (7) Recovery of the water connection between the Guadiamar basin and the Doñana marshlands, ideally through the use of NbS (e.g., floodplain recovery). This measure can be accompanied by the purchase of lands with high environmental value or that can potentially be restored with high interest habitats to be included in the protected areas network [Goal#1, Goal#2]
- (8) Substitution of groundwater resources by other water resources, and increase of water availability (e.g. artificial recharge of aquifers, use of treated wastewater for agriculture, use of desalinated sea water), thus reducing risk of irrigated agriculture under drought periods [Goal#1, Goal#3]
- (9) Payments for the afforestation of irrigated farming areas, with a focus on restoring river forest areas [Goal#1, Goal#2]
- (10) Crops diversification [Goal#3] and creation and promotion of the 'Doñana Biosphere Reserve' brand

[Figure 14](#) provides the linkages between measures towards the achievement of the key Nexus objectives defined as part of the vision scenario.

Figure 14. Priority and accompanying measures towards the Vision scenario

4.4.5. Political economy analysis

This step has built on an analysis of the political-economy and governance contexts within the Water-Ecosystems-Food Nexus. A Political and Economy Analysis (PEA) is a tool used to understand the complex political and economic context within which organisations work. The rationale behind performing a PEA analysis for the Doñana region is to unravel the connections between actors, institutions, and formal and informal norms. This enables to deepen the understanding of the evolution and dynamics of interactions between the political and economic spheres. The outcomes of the analysis provide an orientation for proposing behaviourally informed measures that can be included into more effective strategies.

This is of paramount importance for this case study since this is not the first time that large-scale investments are made in Doñana to try to sort out and reduce existing conflicts in resources allocation. As one of the interviewees pointed out, “Doñana has become a ‘bottomless pit’ that attracts money and initiatives” which have not been delivered as planned (e.g., ‘Doñana 2005 project’ -that was at its time one of the largest world’s wetlands restoration projects-, or the Sustainable Development plans for Doñana approved in 1993 and 2010).

The first step in the PEA analysis has been the organisation of semi-structured interviews to collect the key information from a sectoral and individual point of view, enabling participants to feel in a safe environment where they can anonymously share their thoughts on some potentially cumbersome topics. The main questions included in the script are described in Box 1.

Box 1. Script for the PEA semi-structured interviews

a) Risks:

Informal conversation about the main sectoral risks and challenges

b) Policies:

1. Do you think there are regulations and policies ambitious enough to address these challenges?
 - a. If yes, are they being implemented in practice? Are they effective?
 - b. If no, what kind of regulations or policies are missing, and why?

c) Governance:

2. How is the coordination between different administrations in terms of implementing existing regulations and measures? What administrations do often cooperate between them and what others do not?
3. Do you think there is a relationship of trust between the main actors who have to coordinate to solve the challenges? Do you think everyone understands the existing challenges in the same way?
4. Is there a lack of integrated management policies, or is there a lack of agreement at institutional level?
5. Do you know any good practice in terms of new governance arrangements that has been/might be more effective to address existing challenges (e.g., collective/coordinated actions)?

d) Norms (values) that govern decision-making:

6. What values (e.g., economic, political (votes), social, environmental, cultural, etc.) do you think are imposed on decision-making in practice in order of importance
7. In a crisis situation like the current one, do you think these values change? If so, in what direction and where?

8. To understand the power positions of each key agents: could you reflect on how much power the main agents have in decision-making and why they have this power?

e) Opportunities:

9. What opportunities motivate you in the short and medium term to address the challenges you have mentioned?

A total of 13 people were interviewed representing public administrations, scientists and researchers, the environmental and social sectors, farming sector, and other sectors. Moreover, we conducted two focus groups, one with berry farmers with the support of the Irrigators Communities, and a second one with rural workers, with the support of an association of temporary farm workers. Finally, a specific exercise was included as part of the second workshop to conduct a specific PEA analysis on some of the priority measures, i.e., to achieve a comprehensive understanding of the political, economic, social, and ideological dimensions related to the potential implementation of that measure.

The main list of stakeholders who have been considered for the PEA analysis is composed by:

- a) Public administration: Regional government; Guadalquivir river basin authority; municipalities; Doñana protected area; Doñana 21 foundation; Doñana`s technical Office (National Ministry).
- b) Scientific sector: Doñana Biological Station (CSIC-National Research Council); Universities (Sevilla, Pablo de Olavide, Huelva, Autónoma de Madrid); Spain Geological Survey (IGME); experts in water management (FNCA, individual experts); Spain Oceanography Institute – IEO.
- c) Environmental/Social sectors: Environmental NGOs (WWF, Birdlife, Greenpeace, Scientific Rebellion); Platform ‘Salvemos Doñana’; experts in ecosystems and biodiversity, Farm workers unions.
- d) Farming sector: Individual farmers, farming companies, Irrigators communities (Condado de Huelva, Palos, Fresno), Producers associations (Freshuelva, Puerta de Doñana, ‘Plataforma de defensa de los regadíos del Condado’); Retailers and supermarkets, Technology suppliers; Farming advisors; Certifiers.
- e) Other actors: WRAP initiative; AWS standard; research projects (LIFE Doñana, SNAPquivir); Other.

As a result from this participatory work, we have been able to update the initial stakeholder analysis undertaken in the first year of the LENSES project, as reflected in [Figure 15](#). In this ‘Influence/Interest’ matrix:

- *Influence* is defined here as the capacity/power of an actor to solve or aggravate existing challenges in a climate change context.
- *Interest* is related to the importance of challenges to the actor (i.e., is it in their interest to solve it / is it an important problem for their activity).

This representation has been constructed from the identification of responsibilities and competencies of each actor, and the perceptions shown by the set of actors regarding the capacity/interest of other actors in solving existing problems in the study area. This interest/influence matrix represents the perception at the time of this analysis and is by no means a fixed picture of the relationships between actors, as these can change and evolve over time.

Figure 15. Influence/Interest matrix (updated January 2024)

4.4.6. Contributions to the strategic roadmap: a narrative towards a ‘Resilient Doñana’

The participatory work (i.e., interviews, focus groups, workshops and PEA analysis) has led to the identification of several key inputs (i.e., recommendations and advices) to inform the drafting of a strategic roadmap towards the ‘Resilient Doñana’ scenario. This section provides: i) general recommendations related to governance and policy aspects; ii) more specific recommendations for the implementation of priority measures; and iii) a set of final remarks.

a) Policy and governance

As part of the process, several participants -representing different sectors- agreed that two big issues are: i) the lack of development of cross-cutting policies, and ii) the absence of a clear commitment to a **development and integrated management plan** that incorporates measures designed to consolidate the agricultural sector and guarantee the environmental sustainability of the territory in the short-mid (3-10 years) and longer term (10-20 years). As a result of this lack of ‘systemic thinking’, several of the agents criticised the fact that the measures proposed are aimed at distributing funds to satisfy the aspirations of all parties rather than responding to a well-structured plan with clear objectives and capable of consolidating a model of coexistence between agricultural production and environmental conservation. However, one of the interviewees warns that he/she considers it very complicated that *"the administrations will end up leading the necessary transformation because this process is going to require changes, including job losses, and nobody is going to do it because economic and political criteria still prevail in decision-making"*.

Strong criticisms have been raised by several participants in relation to the lack of this well-structured long-term plan to guide and steer the regional development:

- The absence of a structured plan is a barrier for a more efficient use of the economic resources to change the current model towards a more sustainable socioeconomic model. Most of the planned measures are not assessed in terms of cost-benefit and of their expected efficacy. This is a strong limitation to prioritise the use of the available resources. A shared complaint is that politics' interests do often rule over other implementation criteria. As an example, one interviewee stated that "Doñana has become an 'expert' in demonstrating that misapplied funding does not work". There is an extended perception about a short-term vision of the administrations ("*seeking political gain*" and "*using the money to please everyone*") as a big constraint to apply the optimal solutions to existing challenges.
- This 'short-termism' provokes a reduced contribution of science into decision-making, i.e., "*politicians take decisions without listening to specialists*". A specific request of some scientists and researchers has been the creation of an independent Scientific Advisory Council that can produce recommendations based on good science, and that are partially binding or at least can only be rejected on reasoned grounds.
- Doñana is a space that is "*highly participated*", e.g., through the Doñana's Participation Council and other local or sectoral participation processes. However, the broad perception is that there is no effective participation in decision-making, i.e., "*perception of administrations behaving under 'Enlightened despotism' standards*". This is leading to a lack of social capital and of social support for the governance measures. As an example, many farmers have explained that they are "*fed up of being blamed for everything*" while they "*are developing a very important socio-economic activity for the region in compliance with existing laws and want to be a strong part of the solutions but do not have any room or support to act on this end*". As another example, other non-public sector actors expressed that they have a low involvement in policy design and implementation, despite having the greatest knowledge about the territory, i.e., "*Laws are being made and applied by people who has never been here and live very far away*".
- In Doñana region, the bigger issue is related to governance rather than to a lack of sound policies. Public policies specific to the region have been put into place for many years but these do not sufficiently address transversal issues and have not been mainstreamed. This is partly behind the fact that many of these policies have not been effectively implemented.
- In addition, some actors explained that there has been a lack of cooperation among the agents that are or may be involved in the implementation of the existing policies, strategies or plans. As an example, one participant claimed that "*a big problem is that there are many agents which are accounted for competences in water, land or agricultural management in the region but when any problem comes out, only a few of them take a step forward as responsible to sort out that problem. There are many who want the power but few who want to be responsible*". Many agents perceive a lack of co-ordination between the different levels of administration.
- In addition, there is often a lack of the necessary resources for the implementation of the existing regulation, e.g., required personnel for the monitoring, surveillance and implementation of actions related to the control of illegal farming.

[b\) About potential measures](#)

(1) An effective WEF Nexus management requires comprehensive coordination between various entities

and administrations. A collaborative approach is essential to holistically address Nexus challenges and ensure effective implementation of measures and policies. Coordination reduces duplication of efforts and facilitates a faster and more efficient response.

However, one of the main problems identified in this diagnostic phase is the lack of **collaboration between public administrations**, which stems from a complex distribution of competences at several scales and the prevalence of political criteria over technical criteria in decision-making. A clear example has been the conflict between the regional and national administrations about the proposed regional regulation to legalise illegally farmed areas, and which has been present in mass media for many months.

The coordination between administrations is hindered by excessive bureaucracy, and inertia and resistance to change. Moreover, political interests are seen as a barrier that is difficult to overcome, and that is producing a lack of trust towards the role of the public administrations. The creation of spaces for dialogue with participation of other agents, and the establishment of clear technical criteria for the selection and monitoring of an effective implementation of measures and actions, are perceived as the key opportunities to spark collaboration among public administrations.

(2) As previously mentioned, the lack of coordination and collaboration between administrations has been showcased for the case of **illegal irrigation**, which represents a direct threat to the sustainability of water resources in Doñana. Eliminating this practice will contribute significantly to the conservation and preservation of water bodies by limiting overexploitation. However, there is strong social and economic pressure to maintain illegal irrigation due to the lack of economic alternatives and the absence of a different model. In short, it is an "unpopular" measure especially for the local population, since livelihoods of families are dependent on an illegal activity. Some participants have mentioned a recent report that demonstrates that bigger farms controlled by large companies tend to have water use rights whereas smaller farms have lesser access to water use (FNCA, 2023), which exacerbates social conflicts. Several stakeholders have mentioned the existence of local interests that limit the effectiveness of measures to control and eliminate illegality in irrigation, *"this occurs in all municipalities, irrespective of the political party that is governing"*. Therefore, it was concluded that the planned accompanying measure to improve water governance in the area is of critical importance to reduce illegal water use.

The CHG is actively working to solve this problem, and has closed down hundreds of illegal boreholes in the last years. Even though the legal system provides strong guarantees to the water users, and it takes long time (i.e., 2-4 years) to conclude the required administrative process. There is a good consensus on the importance of providing the necessary resources to enforce the law in terms of monitoring and sanctioning capacity.

The designation of the Rocina, Almonte and Marismas groundwater bodies as at risk of not achieving a good quantitative status (i.e., overexploited) has opened the door to the General Attorney Office to intervene in those cases where overabstraction or not allowed use of water and land is producing a direct effect on the protected habitats and species. These are criminal rather than administrative processes, which can lead to more severe consequences (prison sentences instead of fines). This is also a proper incentive that can drive reductions in illegal water use.

(3) The setting up and consolidation of the groundwater user communities (CUAs) is assessed as a measure of high efficacy to achieve the objective of improving quantitative status of the groundwater bodies. Empowering CUAs to manage their own water resources not only fosters shared responsibility, but also allows to implement strategies to be tailored to the specific needs of the region. This promotes water use

efficiency and the implementation of sustainable practices.

As contemplated by the Doñana 2030 Action Plan, the elaboration of action programmes for each groundwater bodies to be managed by the CUA, is agreed as a core action. This program should include the management of an annual groundwater abstraction plan (including control of illegal irrigation), improved monitoring of groundwater levels, or the substitution of individual wells by community abstractions. The main barriers to be overcome are regulatory restrictions (i.e., rigidity of the law) and the reluctance to change (i.e., novel governance and management systems) of public administrations.

(4) In 2015, the National Government acquired the 'Los Mimbrales' estate, with an extension of more than 900 hectares, with the objective of contributing to the recovery of the good status of the Almonte-Marismas aquifer. This farm is located within the la Rocina groundwater body, very close to the National Park boundaries and had an estimated annual groundwater withdrawal of 6.8 hm³. Nowadays, this volume of water stays in the aquifer and the measurements of the groundwater levels demonstrate a significant improvement in the aquifer status in this area, which endorses the efficacy of this land purchase. In addition, the farmlands has been renaturalised, including streams restoration, and several biodiversity enhancement actions have been carried out.

The success of this measure supports its replication, although there are no other candidates with a similar extension and location. There is a consensus that this is a good measure although not a fully efficient one, since this is expensive and requires a large investment. Moreover, [land purchase for the reallocation of water rights](#) into environmental use requires of clear criteria for the identification of the priority areas to be acquired. These are not yet provided by the Doñana 2022 Action Plan.

A valuable opportunity would be to purchase sites close to the peridunar area to reduce pressure on the temporary lagoons. The CHG is already carrying out the [relocation of the wells that supply water to Matalascañas](#) touristic site to other areas of the aquifer where water abstractions have less impact on the coastal lagoons and wetlands, so the combined effect of both measures could help a better conservation of these habitats of high environmental value.

(5) In order to reduce groundwater abstraction, land purchase activities and reduction of illegal water use must be accompanied by other actions focusing [on reducing water use in legal farms](#). Reducing the demand for legal irrigation implies the implementation of efficient and sustainable practices in agriculture. This not only contributes to water conservation, but also ensures the availability of the resource for other needs and uses, maintaining a balance between human demands and ecosystem health. In addition, other actions to promote good management practices to enhance biodiversity, deliver ecosystem services and promote the conservation of resources can be implemented.

Innovation and the use of new technologies in farm and water management are seen as key solutions for the agricultural model. Most growers are making efforts to use novel methods to improve the efficiency of water use, as lower availability can affect both the total volume of production and the quality of the produce. Moreover, this can be a driver for a greater incorporation of the local population into agricultural employment through technical jobs. Further support to promote this modernisation and facilitate knowledge transfer is requested to public administrations by farmers and producers.

All these practices could be translated into collective water stewardship actions, in collaboration with other actors of the food value chain – i.e., certifiers, retailers, supermarkets and consumers, to develop groundbreaking business models. For example, agreements that recognise effort of producers who are committed

to practices that reduce resource consumption, preserve or enhance biodiversity, or improve the working conditions of day labourers, and reward these through better prices or business conditions.

Actions for improving working and living conditions of temporary workers in the farming sector are envisaged within the Doñana 2023 Action Plan. The analysis has determined a relationship between illegal irrigation and the vulnerability of day labourers, which was highlighted in the interviews conducted with the Huelva province farm workers' association, as well as in the focus group with farmers in the Corona Norte de Doñana. Therefore, these aspects will need to be considered as part of any agreement, since social justice is a core aspect of any sustainability strategy.

Among the possible lines of work, several actions have been identified, e.g., good irrigation practices, sensorisation and modelisation, public-private programmes for experimental and demonstration trials, hydroponics cultivation with recirculation of water (as a necessary condition to achieve real water savings), or good practices in fertilisation and soil conservation.

Among the barriers, the 2030 agenda and the role of the EU have been identified as tending to impose overly restrictive conditions on production, without resulting in better prices. In this sense, competition from non-EU countries is perceived as a serious problem for the extension of more sustainable cultivation practices, as it is very difficult to compete in the same markets when the quality requirements in production are very different. This creates a dilemma of sustainability vs profitability that only can be addressed through coordinated action of public and private sectors.

(6) In addition to water availability issues, Doñana is also facing water quality problems due to a deficient urban water depuration. The RBMP and the Action Plan for Rural Development 2023 include significant budgets to improve existing [urban sanitation systems and wastewater treatment plants](#) as well as to build new infrastructures where needed. This is assessed as an important measure that will pay dividends in the few next years, i.e., leading to an improvement in water quality of surface water bodies.

(7) The recovery of the natural flooding dynamics of the marshlands through their [reconnection with the Guadiamar basin](#) is another central action for the recovery of the good status of surface water bodies.

The Junta de Andalucía has recently executed the [purchase of lands with high environmental value](#) to be as part of the Action Plan for Rural Development 2023 through the acquisition of the Veta la Palma estate (7,600 hectares by 72.6 M€ - see [Figure 16](#)).

In the last decade, the site has been used as a fish farm, although the lack of water in the marshlands has motivated that many of the wintering birds have moved into the area. The current plan is undertake a restoration plan and to add the site to the National Park (it is already part of the buffer protected area). The main constraint is that currently water is pumped in from the Guadalquivir estuary, and it has to be resolved how these operating costs will be maintained once the economic activity is abandoned.

Figure 16. Location of the 'Veta la Palma' site

This acquisition can be connected the pending recovery of the Brazo de la Torre channel, thus reconnecting part of the marshlands with the Guadalquivir river. This action was approved as part of the Doñana 2005 project but it was never implemented. Furthermore, a wider regeneration of the system includes the recovery of the Guadiamar floodplain and the connection of the Caño Guadiamar stream with the Guadiamar river, without which the middle and upper parts of the marshes get almost disconnected from the fluvial network and do not and benefit from the large winter floods. This is a complex action because it implies an actuation over areas that have been transformed for decades (see [Figure 17](#)) but it is assessed as an indispensable action to recover Doñana. This will also require important decisions about the recovery of water rights and/or the purchase of land.

Figure 17. Former connection of the Guadiamar river and the Caño Guadiamar stream (depicted as a blue line), which provided a strong contribution to the marshlands in wet winters, when Guadiamar river overflowed. The former stream was desiccated and occupied by intensive irrigated farms (see 2020 satellite image)

These actions would allow to preserve a gradient of freshwater to brackish water (through tidal influence) across the marshlands, thus increasing availability of habitats and ecological niches. Moreover, water would be supplied to the entire Veta la Palma without the need for artificial pumping, restoring the old system of pipes and pikes which were filled from the Brazo de la Torre and the Guadalquivir itself.

(8) In the mid-term, another important measure is the substitution of groundwater with other water resources from different origin (treated wastewater or desalinated sea water), or the development of artificial recharge projects that can increase water availability and include resilience against climate change. This is considered as a solution of high efficacy where pressure on groundwater bodies is significant.

Nevertheless, there are some potential drawbacks to these approaches, mainly the need of strong governance agreements and monitoring systems already in place before the execution of any infrastructure or project to increase the offer and availability of water for irrigation. Increasing the availability of the water resources is crucial to address scarcity and ensure the long-term viability of aquatic ecosystems in Doñana. However, this implies strong investments while also has the risk of delivering a 'rebound effect' that increment the pressure over the system by increasing the demand. Again, technical and social criteria needs to be clearly delineated and agreed before undertaking any action, therefore introducing transparency and legitimacy into the process while avoiding that political interests can bias the outcomes.

(9) The Doñana 2023 foresees [payments for the afforestation of farming areas](#). The initial version of the plan does not clarify whether these payments only apply to irrigated lands or can be received by any farming area. The participants in the workshop agreed this can be an effective measure, in particular if it is connected to the restoration of streams and river forest areas. Moreover, they also agreed it should be specified that transformed farmlands need to be currently irrigated under legal conditions.

On the other hand, some of the interviewees are not fond about the implementation of this measure since this may imply the relocation of the farming activity. Many producers could choose to get the funds and invest these in neighbouring regions, in particular if climate change expands the potential cultivation areas for the berries.

(10) Other mid-term solutions to ensure sustainability of the agricultural sector target the diversification of crops and farming options (e.g., agro-ecological practices). There are obvious advantages and opportunities, e.g., increased resilience to market fluctuations and climate change (as the producers have more different income sources and can produce through a broader period), or the broader delivery of ecosystem services, which could be capitalized through novel business models and payment schemes. However, there is a higher knowledge requirement and the learning curve may take a long time, which poses some operational risks. There are high upfront investments (e.g., in machinery) and profitability may decline if production declines and marketing channels are not well established.

A key accompanying measure is the creation and promotion of the 'Doñana Biosphere Reserve' branding. This label aims to give greater visibility and outreach to the products and services originating in the Biosphere Reserves through awareness and communication campaigns targeting national and EU consumers. The purpose of this action is to inform consumers about the environmental and social values that some products and services represent, so they can be willing to pay a higher price to value these.

Stakeholders value this initiative although there are several question marks that need to be resolved. Farmers are currently adopting several certification standards addressing sustainability and environmental aspects. In many cases there is a lack of standardisation at the EU level for these certificates, so producers need to pay for the implementation of many standards when they want to export to EU markets. Many of the farmers and some of the other agents interviewed were critical of the prevailing certification system, pointing out that it has generated a "*certification business*" that falls on farmers and does not do enough to solve existing problems or reduce risks, and that in many cases "*it is a way for intermediaries and distributors to cover their backs*" in the eyes of supermarkets and consumers. Moreover, one of the most widespread complaints is the lack of adaptation of certification standards to local contexts.

A second shortcoming (that could be turned into an advantage) is the lack of implantation of the Doñana 21 label, which was born with a similar aim, but is barely used and remains unknown for Spanish and EU consumers. There are several lessons that can be learned from this experience to better understand what

did not work well, but it provides a nudge about the size of the challenge of engaging with consumers.

As a support action, a consolidated program for awareness raising and environmental education about Doñana at several scales (local, regional, national and EU) is key to help preserve the environmental values of the region. Young people should be a central audience by promoting students visits to the area, and the explanation of international importance of Doñana should be one of the focus of the local campaigns. In the broader scale campaigns, the efforts made in the sustainability of the system (Nexus approach) by local and regional actors should be put in value.

(11) Finally, there are some other accompanying measures that are relatively transversal to the other actions and can facilitate their wider adoption.

The development of a multi-sectoral climate change adaptation plan at a regional scale is considered an important asset to reduce vulnerability and risk of human activities and natural capital and to adapt all measures to evolving climatic contexts. Specific programs for biodiversity monitoring and conservation will be of paramount importance as adaptation measures to changing conditions.

c) Final remarks

Nowadays, Doñana can be considered as a paradigmatic case of conflict in the allocation of water resources between socioeconomic activities (farming and tourism) and environmental conservation. This is a complex challenge in a complex environment, as we ourselves have learned throughout the LENSES stakeholder engagement and participatory processes.

The scenario planning approach that has been developed in the case study has run in parallel to the development of new and far-reaching policy initiatives. We have adapted our process to be able to capture this information and have worked on the production of specific recommendations and information that can inform a wider reflection about the best options to implement the measures that have been recently approved as part of these policies and plans.

The Nexus approach has proven to be a valuable tool to adopt a systemic approach towards the existing challenges. Our work has built on the use of a visioning methodology to create a complete narrative of change from the BAU situation towards a desired future. On top of that, we have added a political-economy analysis layer to better understand what are the factors that can impulse or deter the adoption of the key measures. This is not the first time that ambitious plans and policies are thought out and implemented for Doñana. However, the overall socio-ecologic system is in a critical condition and climate change is exerting an increasing pressure. Why this time it should be different? There are some answers and ideas that regularly came across throughout our interactions with stakeholders, i.e., system thinking, cooperation and collaboration, scientific knowledge, clear decision criteria, participation, long-term planning, dialogue and agreements... in our opinion, these are the key concepts that summarise the value of the Nexus approach and that can really help the region to move towards the resilient Doñana vision.

5. Menemen pilot: key actions to support a wider adoption of a Nexus strategy

In Menemen plain pilot (Gediz basin - Turkey), the Nexus approach is explored as a viable option to minimise the negative effects from climate change into agricultural sustainability and environmental conservation.

5.1. Identification of the key systemic Nexus challenges

In terms of **problem framing**, current climatic conditions and expected climate change are pressuring the sustainability of the agricultural system, which is a central economic activity for the area. For example, high groundwater levels are observed due to precipitation in winter that prevents production and causes drainage in farming plots, whereas drought and dry conditions in summer are causing groundwater levels depletion and soil salinity. Moreover, agricultural sustainability is under threat due to agricultural land decrease.

The **Nexus challenges** have been selected among the most central elements in the CLD (see D4.2) while aiming to adopt a systemic approach. These have been summarized as:

- Optimisation of the interplay between water resources availability and use, and agricultural practices (e.g., increase surface water availability for irrigation and preserve water quality).
- Preserve environmental conditions (e.g., environmental flow of rivers and streams, and conservation of ecosystems related to water) and soil conservation, in particular through the implementation of NBSs.

In order to address these challenges, **sectoral objectives** have been defined as:

- a) WATER: increase efficiency in water use for irrigation, reduction of leakages in the water distribution and application systems, and desalination
- b) ECOSYSTEMS: increase the implementation of NBSs, and restore/increase biodiversity
- c) FOOD: increase cost-efficiency in food production

In addition, the CLD has been analysed to detect potential **Nexus leverage points**, i.e. elements in the system that can accelerate the impacts of policy interventions for addressing the above-mentioned nexus challenges. These are summarised as:

- Improved water allocation planning and agricultural productivity through increase of the farmers' water users' association role and capacities, and the design of targeted agricultural policies and subsidies (including implementation of NBSs).
- Better planning of intensive agriculture, including reduction of unauthorized groundwater abstraction
- Better management and use of agricultural inputs to keep soil fertility and avoid environmental degradation of ecosystems.

5.2. Defining the “Business as Usual” (BAU) scenario

The BAU scenario has been defined for the different Nexus sectors:

- For the water domain, the effects of climate change and related impacts are linked to severe impacts on water resources, in particular to a reduction in available water quantity and problems with water quality related to irrigation activities.
- For the ecosystems domain, the impacts of climate change are perceived as very significant. Land use changes are creating a strong pressure on environment, which is also threatened by the progressing soil degradation. The increasing water demand for productive activities will create an imbalance for environmental flow.
- For the agricultural sector, water availability for irrigation decreases and the reduction in soil fertility limits agricultural production.

The Table 7 summarises the process of elaboration of the BAU scenario.

Table 7. Main aspects for the BAU scenario in the Menemen plain

WATER	Short term (2025-2040)	Medium term (2040-2050)	Long term (2050-2070)
Challenge 1: Access and sharing of water	- decrease in irrigated agriculture - decrease in yield - costs increase	- product variety decreases - socio-economic problems caused by water sharing	- agricultural quality is completely lost - agricultural migration
Challenge 2: Water pollution	- food safety in danger - human health in danger	- scarcity - access to healthy food becomes difficult - soil loss	- scarcity and lack of access to clean water - soil and groundwater pollution
Challenge 3: Salinity	- changing the product pattern	- soil use inefficiency -soil loss	- soil use inefficiency - soil loss and soil pollution
AGRICULTURE	Short term (2025-2040)	Medium term (2040-2050)	Long term (2050-2070)
Challenge 1: Decrease in agricultural production and lands	- increase in consumer price, - production decreases	- decline in rural population, - external dependence	- scarcity, health problems
Challenge 2: Intensive agriculture (excessive input use)	- soil depletion, -increase in diseases and pests	- increase in soil salinity, - decrease in biodiversity	- marginalization of agricultural lands
Challenge 3: Increase in input cost	- profit loss, decrease in agricultural production	- increase in agricultural product imports, product pattern change	- decrease in agricultural sufficiency at national level, unemployment
ECOSYSTEM	Short term (2025-2040)	Medium term (2040-2050)	Long term (2050-2070)
Challenge 1: Drought and Desertification	- productivity decrease, and change in product pattern, - new technologies	- conversion of agricultural into non-agricultural land, - difficulty in accessing good quality water	- deterioration of soil and water resources, - decline in sustainable production, food crisis
Challenge 2: Decrease in biodiversity and natural living environment	- disruption of existing ecosystems, - decrease in endemic Species	- changes in species distribution, - spread of invasive species, - decrease in the number of other species	- decrease / change in biodiversity, - increase in epidemics, - globalisation of local diseases
Challenge 3: Urbanization and industrialization	- decrease in agricultural lands, - increase in the amount of waste	- difficulties in raw material procurement, - destruction of wetlands and eco-corridors	- increase in marginal agricultural lands, - destruction of fertile lands, - sectoral income changes

5.3. A vision for the Nexus in the Menemen plain

Participants in the workshops did not specifically work on the definition of a vision scenario, which was generally identified as the situation where Nexus challenges are adequately tackled.

Stakeholders provided specific feedback on precautions to be taken related to the avoidance of the negative BAU scenarios, which are summarised in Table 8.

Table 8. Precautions to be taken to avoid the BAU scenario in the Menemen plain

WATER	Short term (2025-2040)	Medium term (2040-2050)	Long term (2050-2070)
Challenge 1: Access and sharing of water	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integration of institutions and legislation in water management - Development of policies based on scientific data - Ensuring data supply and security - Ensuring farmers' participation in the System - Adapting water-based product pattern 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of policies based on scientific data - Ensuring data supply and security - Reviewing the water use monitoring mechanisms - Providing alternative water sources - Providing agricultural support against water scarcity - Adapting water-based product pattern - Converting the irrigation network to a closed system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of policies based on scientific data - Ensuring data supply and security - Increasing reservoir capacity - Converting the irrigation network to a closed system - Adapting water-based product pattern
Challenge 2: Water pollution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Periodic pollution monitoring - Strict control of industrial discharges and deterrent measures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Periodic pollution monitoring - Reducing the effects of industrialization on agriculture - Transition to modern irrigation techniques - Updating legislation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transition to modern irrigation techniques
Challenge 3: Salinity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Periodic cleaning of drains - Continuation of ÇATAK (a kind of a subsidy) support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improving water quality - Rehabilitation of drainage systems - Accelerating land reclamation works 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improving water quality - Rehabilitation of drainage systems - Accelerating land reclamation works
AGRICULTURE	Short term (2025-2040)	Medium term (2040-2050)	Long term (2050-2070)
Challenge 1: Decrease in agricultural production and lands	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implementation of new legislation and review on regulations, -increase in inspections 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increasing agricultural subsidies, - Preventing rural migration and land fragmentataion, - Land consolidation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technology use in agriculture, - Developing alternative areas for agriculture, - Expropriation
Challenge 2: Intensive agriculture (excessive input use)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of organic materials, reduced tillage, adapting - Alternative agricultural training methods, good agricultural practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New techniques and measures to increase productivity, - Transition to crop patterns that require less water, - Sustainable agricultural practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tax systems based on carbon and water footprint
Challenge 3: Increase in input cost	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increasing subsidies, supporting R&D activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Export restrictions on strategic inputs and raw materials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increasing domestic production

ECOSYSTEM	Short term (2025-2040)	Medium term (2040-2050)	Long term (2050-2070)
Challenge 1: Drought and Desertification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dissemination of drought resistant varieties, - Dissemination of varieties resistant to diseases and pests, - Effective protection of fertile soils 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dissemination of climate-suitable/climate-sensitive varieties, - Dissemination of necessary technologies to prevent waste of water, - Utilisation of domestic waste water, - Regulation of the legal framework. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of seawater desalination techniques, - Development of new water, conservation methods - Establishment of an ecosystem ministry (ecosystem-based management systems)
Challenge 2: Decrease in biodiversity and natural living environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of a dynamic spraying model, - Development of agro-ecological methods, - Conservation of local varieties 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Different applications in control methods, - Optimisation of local varieties, - Dissemination of bioenergy systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Making the use of local varieties compulsory, - Balanced (fair) distribution and management of natural resources, - Bioremediation
Challenge 3: Urbanization and industrialization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promoting clean production, - Planning urbanisation and industrialisation according to the production plan, - Supervision of waste management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increasing green and sink areas, - Making green energy compulsory and making it widespread 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Producers coming together for the same purpose, - Development of an integrated management system

5.4. Supporting a strategic roadmap towards a resilient WEF Nexus in Menemen

The analysis has focused on the selection of several measures that can be efficient to reduce the potential impacts of existing challenges over the WEF Nexus. Then, a specific exercise was undertaken in the final workshop to assess the barriers and opportunities for each sector. These results are summarised within Table 9.

Table 9. Priority measures and analysis of main barriers and opportunities: Menemen plain

Solution/ Measure (WATER)	Barriers			Opportunities
	Socioeconomic	Legal	Others	
Intermural integration and legislation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Culture of reconciliation, - Insufficiency of farmers' organizations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Vast number of legislation, - Authorization of more than one institution 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of participatory management, - Low participation of the private sector and NGOs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New Ministry's planning initiatives, - Increased awareness of climate change impacts (droughts)
Supporting the operation of treatment facilities and creating effective recovery management plans	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of profit, high cost 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Legislation difficult to implement, especially at some local areas 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Failure to apply the "polluter pays" principle 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Competence of private companies to deliver services - Increase in awareness, - New regulations

Rehabilitation of drainage systems (at field and network level)	- High cost, lack of awareness, - Economic inadequacy of producers	- Lack of subsidies		- Development of new technologies, - Reduced costs in accessing technology
Solution/ Measure (AGRICULTURE)	Barriers			Opportunities
	Socioeconomic	Legal	Others	
Strengthening legislation and law enforcement	- Traditionalism	- Insufficiency of penalties and sanctions	-	- Taking part in international agreements
sustainable agriculture	- Conventional agriculture, increase in costs	- Complexity of legal procedure	-	- Availability of loans and subsidies
Increasing domestic production	- Conventional agriculture, - Low competitiveness	-		- Availability of local natural resources and biodiversity
Solution/ Measure (ECOSYSTEM)	Barriers			Opportunities
	Socioeconomic	Legal	Others	
Implementation of ecosystem-based management systems	- Economic concerns	- Inadequacy of incentives	- Challenges of implementation - The difficulty in changing habits	- Increased biodiversity
Dissemination of bioenergy systems	- Economic concerns	-Lack of legal regulations	- Conflicts of interest - Lack of knowledge	- Protection of natural resources
Making green energy compulsory and widespread	- High investment costs	-Lack of legal regulations	-Adaptation challenges	-Reduced pollution

The feedback of the participants in this exercise was very positive when evaluated from the perspective of those who benefited from the project outcomes. Additionally, visioning implementation raised the awareness on the challenges and the current situation of Menemen Plain among a broad range of stakeholders.

6. Pinios pilot: key actions to support a wider adoption of a Nexus strategy

The Pinios pilot has implemented a participatory approach, through a series of three intertwined workshops, supported by semi-structured interviews to identify the central Nexus challenges and objectives (section 6.1), and then, to identify and prioritise several measures that can help tackle these challenges (sections 6.2 and 6.3). Some complementary analyses have produced key information to support the potential implementation of these measures (section 6.4).

6.1. Identification of the key systemic Nexus challenges

The Pinios River Basin (PRB) is one of the most productive basins of Greece and the national WFD pilot basin. Within the LENSES project, two areas of the PRB are analyzed, namely the Agia watershed and the Pinios River Delta (PRD). In terms of **problem framing**, the high-water consumption (for both areas) and the groundwater over-abstraction (for Agia) for irrigation (see D8.1) is a core challenge because irrigation constitutes the dominant water use. Water resources are, in general, considered sufficient but issues can arise with the peak irrigation demand in dry years, which is expected to be aggravated by climate change.

From the environmental point of view, the PRD has an important value although the conversion of the natural landscape to agricultural land is affecting the ecosystems, e.g., salinization phenomena are being observed and high NO₃⁻ concentrations have been locally measured. High NO₃⁻ concentrations are also locally observed in Agia watershed. Current climatic conditions and expected climate change are pressuring the sustainability of the agricultural system, which is a central economic activity for both areas. Over the past decade, there has been a substantial increase in kiwi fruit cultivation in the PRD, with the cultivation area nearly doubling. Kiwi fruit cultivation requires irrigation with low-salinity water, which is primarily sourced from surface water abstracted from the main Pinios River course. Groundwater salinity levels in PRD are unsuitable for this purpose. Consequently, the irrigation demands of the PRD's most rapidly expanding crop are reliant on water from the Pinios River, the availability of which can fluctuate significantly during drought periods. In contrast, in the Agia watershed, irrigation needs are predominantly met through groundwater. However, there is typically a local decrease in groundwater availability for irrigation towards the end of the irrigation season, particularly during dry spells.

The main sectoral **Nexus challenges** have been elicited from the CLD that is described within D4.2 and is one of the results of the participatory approach activities, and have also been agreed with local and regional stakeholders through the participatory workshops:

- Water: achieving and maintaining sufficient quantity and good quality of water resources
- Food: sustainability of the agricultural sector
- Environment: protection and restoration of ecosystems

As a starting point, a specific exercise was conducted to characterise the main problems associated to each challenge, as well as to carry out an initial analysis of the main: i) obstacles and inhibitors; ii) risks and impacts; iii) strengths and opportunities; and iv) indicators to monitor how each challenge can be addressed (see Table 10).

Table 10. Characterisation of the main challenges in Pinios pilot

CHALLENGE 1: Achieving and maintaining sufficient quantity and good quality of water resources
Problems
Spatial and temporal variation of the groundwater level in the Agia watershed
Locally high nitrate concentrations in groundwater
Lack of infrastructure projects (irrigation networks, reservoirs)
Obstacles, Inhibitors
Lack of efficient water consumption audit in the agricultural sector, lack of GW control and limited monitoring
Irrational behaviors (for irrigation) and sense of water ownership at farm level
Insufficient land planning and management, absence of a specialized regional/rural development plan
Risks, Impacts
Desertification of agricultural areas
Reduction of agricultural production
Strengths/Opportunities
High availability of groundwater during normal climatic conditions
Plenty of studies have been carried out regarding Pinios pilot for the future
Knowledge of quantity of surface and ground water
Availability of extensive monitoring data
Sustainability of the region in terms of water sufficiency appears feasible on the basis of monitoring data
Indicators
Groundwater availability (level, volume) [in relation to the highest rainfall]
Surface water use, by category of use
Groundwater use, by category of use
CHALLENGE 2: Sustainability of the agricultural sector
Problems
Increased production cost
Irrational use of pesticides and other agricultural supplies
Limiting available markets for agricultural exports
Obstacles, Inhibitors
Lack of support and guidance at farming (also for financial tools)
Inefficient subsidies policy (e.g. for young farmers)
Land fragmentation
Risks, Impacts
Unsustainability & abandonment of agricultural sector as a cumulative result of international agricultural markets crisis, low product market value and increased production costs
Increase in youth unemployment
Concentration of crops to few people
Strengths/Opportunities
High-quality products
Geographical position
High availability of soil and crop cultivation data
Implementation of agroecological practices
Indicators
Cost / Profit of agricultural production per unit area
Yield per crop and unit area
Irrigation costs (water, energy, environmental fee, maintenance) per m3 or ha
CHALLENGE 3: Protection and restoration of ecosystems
Problems
Preservation of the ecological flow of the Pinios River
High pressures on the riparian habitats of the Pinios River
Irrational management of used agricultural packaging
Obstacles, Inhibitors
Lack of easy access to EU and national funding
Bureaucracy and fragmentation of responsibilities, limited coordination

Overlapping responsibilities
Risks, Impacts
Destruction of the Delta and salinization of groundwater and soils from the reduction of the ecological flow of the Pinios river
Ecological destruction of water, birds, soil and food/loss of species
Risk of interrupted river flow/supply
Water quality degradation (groundwater and surface)
Strengths/Opportunities
Important areas belong to NATURA
Good water/environmental condition
Rich biodiversity
Existing knowledge about ecosystems and biodiversity
Indicators
Ecological flow of the Pinios river

The main **systemic Nexus challenges** relate to:

- Agricultural productivity and sustainability, with a focus on irrigated agriculture to ensure surface water and groundwater availability for irrigation and considering effectiveness of water allocation criteria.
- Optimisation of the use of chemicals and fertilizers in agriculture to ensure the achievement of appropriate water quality.
- Ensure flora and fauna conservation as well as the maintenance of the ecological flow in rivers and streams

In order to address these challenges, the **sectoral objectives** have been defined as:

- a) WATER: increase efficiency in water use for irrigation, increase awareness of farmers on capillary rise contribution to crop water needs fulfilment
- b) ECOSYSTEMS: increase the implementation of NBSs, maintain or improve the conservation status of ecosystems
- c) FOOD: Crop management improvement to increase extreme events resilience, secure farmers' income against fluctuations of agricultural inputs costs.

In addition, the CLD has been analysed to detect potential **Nexus leverage points**, i.e. elements in the system that can accelerate the impacts of policy interventions for addressing the above-mentioned nexus challenges. These are summarised as:

- i) Measures to support agricultural sustainability:
 - training on good practices,
 - funding,
 - awareness on sustainable water management and water conservation.
- ii) Measures to support environmental conservation:
 - land use planning,
 - environmental awareness level.
- iii) Water quality measures:
 - environmental awareness level,
 - training on good practices.

6.2. Defining the “Business as Usual” (BAU) and vision scenarios

A specific activity was organised in the second workshop to identify key components for the BAU scenario and for the future condition they desire for the region. The session started with an introduction to the pessimistic side, by asking the participants how they consider the pilot areas would be like without their contribution and mobilization, i.e. a business as usual approach with no interventions. Then, the activity continued with an analysis of the bright/optimistic side and they proposed keywords reflecting the future of the Pinios Delta and the Agia sub-basin following resolution of the identified challenges through the interventions proposed by LENSES project. The MentiMeter platform was utilized for the above processes. The results are shown in [Figure 18](#).

Figure 18. Key components of the BAU and vision scenarios in Pinios pilot

6.3. Supporting a strategic roadmap towards a resilient WEF Nexus in Pinios

6.3.1. Identification of measures

As part of the second workshop, the participants discussed about existing challenges and objectives, and were requested to propose measures to tackle these and to regionalize these measures to meet Agia’s sub-basin and Pinios Delta WEF goals. Stakeholders examined each goal separately, and proposed various measures in an effort to secure them. As a follow-up activity, an online questionnaire was circulated to complete the collection of potential measures. The list of measures compiled in the workshop is presented in Table 11.

Table 11. Proposed measures for the Pinios pilot

Challenge 1: Achieving and maintaining sufficient quantity and good quality of water resources	
Goals	Proposed measures
Reduction of spatial and temporal variation of groundwater level in Agia watershed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Irrigation scheduling
Increasing the availability of water resources covering irrigation needs during droughts in the Pinios Delta	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crop restructuring - Switching to crops with less water requirements • Construction of dams on the north side of Kissavos between Omolio and Stomio

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction of reservoirs for storage of winter runoff
Improving the efficiency of water distribution and application systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction of underground water distribution systems • Rational irrigation management - Irrigation scheduling
Restoration of salinitation of groundwater in the Pinios Delta	-
Restoration of locally high nitrate concentrations in groundwater	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rational use of pesticides and fertilizers - Switching to agroecological practices of weed and biomass management
Ensuring surface water availability	-
Challenge 2: Sustainability of the agricultural sector	
Goals	Proposed measures
Reduction of production cost	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Irrigation scheduling • Creation of well-organized cooperatives and farmers' groups
Rational use of pesticides and other agricultural supplies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Choice of sustainable production methods • Network of sensors for monitoring soil quality characteristics
Finding available markets for agricultural exports	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of well-organized cooperatives for improving negotiation skills • Establishment of brand name (marketing campaign) • Organic cultivation of kiwi and other products
Maintainance of high agricultural productivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crop restructuring with more productive varieties Education of farmers and pilot testing of new cultivation methods • Upgrade of irrigation systems
Reduction – Mitigation of crop sensitivity to drought in the Pinios Delta	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crop restructuring - Switching to crops with less water requirements
Challenge 3: Protection and restoration of ecosystems	
Goals	Proposed measures
Ensuring the environmental flow in Pinios River	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Removal of obstructions from riverbeds • Monitoring network for area security • Compilation of a hydrological study for the management of Pinios river
Restoration and conservation of the riparian habitats of the Pinios River	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring the environmental flow in Pinios River • Construction of infrastructure projects for agrotourism
Rational management of used agricultural packaging	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of the legislative framework and cooperation between the involved bodies • Formation of management bodies through the District of Thessaly
Rational use of pesticides, fertilizers, and other agricultural supplies	-
Access to drinkable water for wild species in the mountainous domain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regulation of spring water captured by private works at the slopes of - Kissavos area

6.3.2. Prioritisation of measures

In a subsequent phase of the project, the proposed measures needed to be assessed and prioritized. For this purpose, the contribution of stakeholders is needed to determine weighting factors for a series of evaluation criteria. These criteria were selected following intensive discussions with scientific partners and stakeholders. The definitions of these eight criteria are provided below:

- Criterion 1 - Urgency and efficiency time:** The necessity or priority of a solution adoption/implementation for the immediate fulfillment of defined goals. We take for granted that European policies and the associated national commitments have been developed aiming at Nexus sectors security promotion within the context of climate crisis. Urgency is therefore also intertwined with the satisfaction of the obligations arising from these policies. It also concerns the required time period for the effects of a solution to appear, and also the expected time period for a solution functionality to remain at high standard levels (e.g. project lifetime).
- Criterion 2 - Effectiveness:** The degree of a goal satisfaction for which a solution is designed, adopted and implemented. The effects of the implementation of the solution on the satisfaction of the goal are examined, along with its robustness to climate change (i.e. can the proposed solution withstand the anticipated climate extremes? For example, the construction of a large reservoir with the simultaneous reduction of water resources).
- Criterion 3 - Co-benefits and Intersectionality:** Positive side effects on third sectors that a solution can cause to natural (promoting ecosystems services i.e. the direct and indirect contributions of ecosystems to human wellbeing, and have an impact on our survival and quality of life) and artificial environment and fulfillment of a wide range of goals and targets by the implementation of a single solution, particularly in case of goals and targets referring to different Nexus sectors. For example, a reservoir construction for flood mitigation enhances employment (positive side effect) and also contributes to groundwater supply, water storage, development of small-scale hydroelectric projects, biodiversity enhancement, irrigation water availability enhancement, and ecotourism development. These goals primarily concern the water sector, and in parallel, goals related to all the other Nexus sectors are simultaneously fulfilled.
- Criterion 4 - Negative side effects:** The negative side effects that a solution can cause to natural and artificial environment (e.g., effects on environmental status, labor market, and products added value). For example, a water reservoir construction reduces the available cultivated area (negative side effect on third sector).
- Criterion 5 - Maturity and enabling environment:** The administrative and techno-economic readiness to implement a solution (existing technical knowledge, financial means availability, existence of appropriate administrative mechanisms to support solution implementation, consensus of decision- and policy-makers, conducive government arrangements, supportive policies, opportunities in policies, technical capacity, funding and financing mechanisms and NBS management, etc.) as well as the time required for a solution' implementation to initiate.
- Criterion 6 - Acceptance:** The level of socio-economic acceptance of a solution by the locals and generally affected groups of citizens and their economic activities. The possible development of conflicting interests and their intensity are examined, as well as the level of acceptance of the solution by society.
- Criterion 7 - Sustainability:** A full geographic coverage of an implemented solution is required to ensure equal distribution of generated benefits among the various stakeholder groups, without causing damage to any of these groups. The examination of the potential development of favorable treatment conditions for groups of citizens or economic activities/interests is of great importance. It also concerns the environmental sustainability, the level to which a proposed solution improves or at least does not degrade the environment for future generations.

- **Criterion 8 - Cost:** Qualitative estimation of the direct cost of a solution adoption/implementation: How high or low you assess the total direct cost related to the required studies and the construction/ implementation of a given solution.

A questionnaire (Google Form) was sent to the stakeholders and the scientific partners. The evaluation of the importance of each criterion was performed on a ten-grades scale, so each one of the final 8 criteria could be assigned a weight in the form of an integer from 1-10. A total of 13 partners from both LENSES and H2020 REXUS projects, and 12 stakeholders responded to this questionnaire and the results are depicted in [Figure 19](#).

Figure 19. Weighting of the prioritisation criteria in Pinios

The final list of proposed measures were processed for homogenization and uniformity and sent to the stakeholders in a questionnaire with relevant instructions for their evaluation. The evaluation was based on the score of each of the 8 criteria on a five-grade scale (1- lowest to 5-highest), depending on the importance of each criterion for each measure. The responses received from this phase were analyzed to determine the prioritization of the proposed measures using a weighting average.

In cases where a stakeholder did not assign a score on some of the eight criteria, the gaps were filled with the average of the rest of the scores with which he/she rated the respective measure. However, in some cases where some stakeholders had scored only 1 or 2 criteria on a measure, it was decided not to include that response at all in the calculations so as not to bias the results.

The final score assigned to each measure was calculated as the weighted average of all the received responses. For each goal within each challenge, the measure with the highest score was selected, and its multiplicity in other goals and challenges was checked. Multiplicity prevailed when the difference in scores between the assessed measures was less than or equal to 0.09. If the difference was greater, the measure with the higher score was preferred. Multiplicity was considered when the same measure was referenced in more than one goal and/or challenge.

Based on all the above, the final ranking and selection of the top 2 ranked measures for achieving each goal were identified (Table 12).

Table 12. Priority measures for the Pinios pilot

Goal	Priority measure (1)	Priority measure (2)
Reduction of spatial and temporal variation of groundwater level in Agia sub-basin	Construction of surface water runoff conservation works (reservoirs, lagoons), mountain hydrology projects and rainwater collection systems	Rational irrigation management - Implementation of irrigation scheduling (including deficit irrigation)
Increasing the availability of water resources covering irrigation needs during droughts in the Pinios Delta	Construction of surface water runoff conservation works (reservoirs, lagoons), mountain hydrology projects and rainwater collection systems	Implementation of modern (efficient) irrigation systems (e.g., sub-surface irrigation, drip irrigation, microirrigation, etc.) and precision agriculture
Improving the efficiency of water distribution and application systems	Rational irrigation management - Implementation of irrigation scheduling (including deficit irrigation)	Improvement of water transport and distribution systems (closed irrigation networks, underground networks, fault detection and repair)
Restoration of salinisation of groundwater in the Pinios Delta	Limitation of withdrawals from underground waters in saline and prone to salinization zones	Abandonment of water abstraction projects within salinization zones – transition to high-quality water sources
Restoration of locally high nitrate concentrations in groundwater	Conducting soil analyses for the proper application of fertilization	Rational use of agrochemicals (fertilizers and pesticides) and prescription of agrochemicals
Increasing the availability of surface water	Construction of surface water runoff conservation works (reservoirs, lagoons), mountain hydrology projects and rainwater collection systems	Establishment of quality monitoring services at a regional level (e.g., using bioindicators) for ecosystems and the tightening of prescribed financial or other penalties in cases of pollution violations
Reduction of production cost	Improvement of advisory support structures	Rational irrigation management - Implementation of irrigation scheduling (including deficit irrigation)
Rational use of pesticides and other agricultural supplies	Transition to agroecological practices for weed and biomass management (e.g., Mechanical destruction and incorporation of crop residues)	Systematic information, guidance, and training for irrigators – Utilization of local Media
Finding available markets for agricultural exports	Construction of refrigeration units for the agricultural cooperative of Omolio with the aim of preserving products (mainly kiwis)	Establishment of well-organized cooperatives and farmer groups, and collaboration among them
Maintenance of high agricultural productivity	Conducting soil analyses for the proper application of fertilization	Rational irrigation management - Implementation of irrigation scheduling (including deficit irrigation)
Reduction – Mitigation of crop sensitivity to drought in the Pinios Delta	Construction of surface water runoff conservation works (reservoirs, lagoons), mountain hydrology projects and rainwater collection systems	Restructuring of crops – Transition to crops with lower water requirements - Cultivation of drought-resistant varieties

Goal	Priority measure (1)	Priority measure (2)
Ensuring the environmental flow in Pinios River	Removal of obstacles (sediment) - riverbed cleaning	Partial or complete restoration of hydromorphological features (in specific cases)
Restoration and conservation of the riparian habitats of the Pinios River	Establishment of a monitoring and assessment network for the qualitative characteristics of the soil	Construction of agrotourism infrastructure projects
Rational management of used agricultural packaging	Systematic information, guidance, and training for irrigators - Utilization of local Media	Establishment of management bodies for used agricultural packaging through the Region of Thessaly
Rational use of pesticides, fertilizers, and other agricultural supplies	Conducting soil analyses for the proper application of fertilization	Transition to agroecological practices for weed and biomass management (e.g., Mechanical destruction and incorporation of crop residues)
Access to drinking water for wildlife in the mountainous region	Construction of surface water runoff conservation works (reservoirs, lagoons), mountain hydrology projects and rainwater collection systems	Release (portion) of the water from the springs collected by private projects on the slopes of Kissavos

The four top ranked measures were:

- (1) Efficient soil water management through irrigation scheduling [NBS]
- (2) Improvement of advisory and support structures [GOVERNANCE]
- (3) Construction of water-saving projects (small dams, reservoirs), mountain hydrology, rainwater harvesting systems [GREY]
- (4) Agroecological practices for weed and biomass management (e.g., mulching) [NBS]

6.3.3. Key actors and power dynamics to be considered for the implementation of priority measures

As a final step, stakeholders were requested to identify the actors that are involved, and their incentives in relation to the implementation of each of the priority measures. Then, additional information was collated in relation to the behaviour of each actor, including ways of thinking, power to implement the measure, formal role, and informal role. This set of questions focus on characterizing the key agents that could implement key nexus solutions.

The key questions to facilitate the activity were:

1. List the main actors that would be involved to address the challenge/ implement the solution. What is their future incentive(s) to solve the problem/ apply the measure? How are their current mindsets?
2. What confers them power? (Power and resources to influence the challenge)
3. What ways of thinking and working (formal and informal) influence the sector? What is the stakeholders' formal role? Does the actor also have an informal role? Characterise the formal- informal dynamics if any.

The 4 final top ranked measures were divided in two different categories/posters (technical and governance) to save some time and ensure the completion of this activity with the active participation of the stakeholders during the final workshop. Stakeholders examined each poster separately. The results from this process are compiled in Table 13.

Table 13. Key actors, incentives and behaviour in relation to the priority measures in the Pinios pilot

TECHNICAL SOLUTIONS (NBS and grey solutions)		
KEY ACTORS	INCENTIVES	POWER AND ROLES
Ministry of Rural Development and Food & Ministry of the Environment and Energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incentives for acceleration: Environmental protection legislation. National policy. Resources pricing (water, energy). Infrastructure. • Current way of thinking: Political cost. Comply with Water Framework Directive. Comply with Nitrates Directive. Unemployment/prosperity indicators. Climatic crisis. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power and resources to influence the challenge: institutionalized role and management of financial instruments. Malfunction due to unfavourable organization. Speed of processing procedures • Formal role: Strategy planning. Management and formulation of financial instruments • Informal role: Supporting local needs over others. Interconnection with other bodies and trade union organisations.
Regional and local authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incentives for acceleration: Unemployment/prosperity indicators. Ensuring natural resources. • Current way of thinking: Political gain. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power and resources to influence the challenge: Understaffing. Lack of resources. Inability to choose how to allocate funds. Proximity to recipients and understanding of problems. Speed of processing procedures. • Formal role: Implementation of legislation and strategy. Management of financial tools. • Informal role: Interconnection with other bodies and trade union organisations.
Agricultural education and training bodies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incentives for acceleration: Training/ Education. Unemployment/welfare indicators. Sustainability of agricultural corporations. • Current way of thinking: Support and guidance for young farmers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power and resources to influence the challenge: Understaffing. Insufficient funding. Insufficient infrastructure. Strong institutional role and social acceptance. • Formal role: Training and education of young farmers. • Informal role: Interconnection with production sector/bodies/individuals.
Agricultural cooperatives and individual farmers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incentives for acceleration: Reduction of production costs. Sustainability of agricultural corporation. Production security. Obtaining financial resources. Obtaining subsidies. • Current way of thinking: Survival. Investigation - adaptation to the climate crisis. Increase of profit. Infrastructure. Connection with foreign markets. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power and resources to influence the challenge: Partnership for the development and implementation of innovative tools. Food security. • Formal role: Food production. GDP formation. Shaping the trade balance. • Informal role: Policy Formulation. Formulation of export planning. GDP formation. Shaping the trade balance.
Research/academic institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incentives for acceleration: Climate crisis. Study and management proposals of natural resources. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power and resources to influence the challenge: Support structures. Partnerships with research and production networks. Formulate

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current way of thinking: Boosting innovation. Application of modern methods and tools in applied science. 	<p>and offer proven solutions (and implementation of them).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formal role: Research, training and pilot-scale implementation. Dissemination of knowledge. Transfer of new knowledge. • Informal role: Connection with other bodies. Guidance for bodies. Staffing/ Understaffing of bodies.
GOVERNANCE SOLUTIONS (Improvement of advisory/support structures)		
KEY ACTORS	INCENTIVES	POWER AND ROLES
Financial system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incentives for acceleration: Profit. • Current way of thinking: Sustainability of the agri-food sector. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power and resources to influence the challenge: Investment in schemes, modernisation infrastructure. Management of financial tools. Proper management of capital. • Formal role: Financing of investment and cash flow needs. Business development. Management and investment of funds. • Informal role: Local community development. Contribution to strategy formulation.
Research/academic institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incentives for acceleration: Climate crisis. Study and proposals of natural resources management. • Current way of thinking: Establishment of a legal framework for the application of innovative methods. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power and resources to influence the challenge: Link between research and agencies/ministries. • Formal role: They are attached to a ministry (rural development and food/environment and energy).
Ministry of Rural Development and Food & Ministry of the Environment and Energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incentives for acceleration: Organisation of bodies. Expertise of bodies. • Current way of thinking: Comply with Water Framework Directive. Comply with Nitrates directive. 	
Agricultural cooperatives and individual farmers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incentives for acceleration: Raising public awareness. Certification bodies. Reduction of production costs. Production security and sustainability. Subsidies. Financial tools. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formal role: Food production. GDP formation

6.3.4. Final remarks

The series of workshops in the Pinios pilot served as a testament to the stakeholders' unwavering commitment, viewing their participation not merely as an obligation but as an opportunity for meaningful contribution and collaboration.

Their willingness, energy, and abundance of ideas illuminated the discussions, reflecting a shared aspiration to address the complex challenges within the Pinios pilot areas and explore the intricate dynamics of the NEXUS system. The responses and discussions shared many perspectives, with stakeholders from diverse sectors demonstrating a keen interest in proposing solutions and charting a path towards sustainable development. Their constructive engagement underscored a deep belief in the collective capacity to effect

positive change and navigate the complexities of interconnected socio-economic and environmental systems.

Furthermore, stakeholders expressed a high level of satisfaction with the tools and methodologies employed throughout the project, highlighting their effectiveness in facilitating meaningful dialogue, analysis, and decision-making. The final selection of four measures to address identified challenges earned widespread approval, with stakeholders particularly pleased with their involvement in shaping the outcomes of the project. Importantly, stakeholders emphasized the benefits derived from their engagement over three years, affirming the value of collaboration and knowledge exchange in fostering mutual learning and capacity building.

Their willingness to continue contributing and participating in future projects underscores a shared commitment to sustained progress and collective action towards common goals. This willingness stems also from the fact they felt being offered a floor for their voices to be systematically heard, **resulting in several proposed measures to be included in the latest revision of the regional Water Resources Management Plan** (Hellenic Ministry of Environment and Energy, 2023; Sympraxis Team, 2023). Characteristic measures have also been scientifically evaluated, justified and acknowledged.

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